

Harnessing root-soil-microbiota interactions for drought-resilient cereals

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ABSTRACT

Cereal plants form complex networks with their associated microbiome in the soil environment. A complex system including variations of numerous parameters of soil properties and host traits shapes the dynamics of cereal microbiota under drought. These multifaceted interactions can greatly affect carbon and nutrient cycling in soil and offer the potential to increase plant growth and fitness under drought conditions. Despite growing recognition of the importance of plant microbiota to agroecosystem functioning, harnessing the cereal root microbiota remains a significant challenge due to interacting and synergistic effects between root traits, soil properties, agricultural practices, and drought-related features. A better mechanistic understanding of root-soil-microbiota associations could lead to the development of novel strategies to improve cereal production under drought. In this review, we discuss the root-soil-microbiota interactions for improving the soil environment and host fitness under drought and suggest a roadmap for harnessing the benefits of these interactions for drought-resilient cereals. These methods include conservative trait-based approaches for the selection and breeding of plant genetic resources and manipulation of the soil environments.

1. Introduction

Intensive agriculture and improper land management practices have resulted in soil degradation and poor soil quality, which is currently worsened by the effects of climate change (Ayangbenro et al., 2022). Soil degradation is accompanied by depleted soil organic matter and organic carbon and a loss of microbiological diversity and their biological functions (Wagg et al., 2021). Recent studies have shown that climate change is reducing soil's capacity to perform fundamental processes and functions, such as nutrient cycling, litter decomposition, and organic matter mineralization (Bogati and Walczak, 2022). This has led to increasing concerns that the reduced soil biodiversity may have negative impacts on the ecosystem's functions (Wagg et al., 2021), putting in danger the agroecosystems' productivity and sustainability. However, evidence from studies of plant root microbial functioning suggests that root traits are important predictors of microbial community compositions and functions and their response to a changing climate (de Vries et al., 2016; Williams et al., 2020). For example, plants exude a variable but substantial amount of photosynthesis-derived carbon under drought stress creating a diverse chemical milieu in the form of root exudates, which play fundamental roles in root microbiome

assemblage (de Vries et al., 2019), and hence carbon and nitrogen cycles in soil. Plant root architectural traits such as root-specific length and root hairs interact with beneficial soil microorganisms and play important roles in carbon and nutrient cycles and enzyme activities (Meier et al., 2020; Zhang et al., 2020a). Targeting the trait-based approach underground can thereby impact a range of soil-based ecosystem functions and support soil fertility.

Drought is one of the most significant threats to cereal yields and is expected to become more frequent and intense with climate change (Webber et al., 2018). Drought can alter root traits, such as root diameter, tissue density, specific length, or specific surface area (Galindo-castañeda et al., 2022; Lozano et al., 2022), root exudates (Gargallo-garriga et al., 2018; Ghatak et al., 2022), and plant immune system (Wang et al., 2021; Zhang et al., 2020b), which can change soil biota composition (Breitkreuz et al., 2021), assembly (Gao et al., 2020; Xie et al., 2021), and function (Fitzpatrick et al., 2018; Methe et al., 2019). These shifts in soil microbial communities can be linked with the response of root traits to drought stress (Lozano et al., 2022) and strongly depend on the plant's genetic identity (Fitzpatrick et al., 2018; Kuerban et al., 2023), and to some extent in plant physiology and metabolism under drought (Xu and Coleman-derr, 2019). Nevertheless,

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altered microbial community composition and assembly can be associated with functional changes in microbiota (Gao et al., 2022), which can shape the host response to drought (Carter et al., 2023; Pande et al., 2023). Plant adaptation to drought in the short term is driven by the microbiome associated with the plant (Xu et al., 2018; Yang et al., 2020). However, in the long term, droughts will be directed by the evolutionary interactions occurring between the microbiome and its plant host (Santos-medellín et al., 2021; Schmidt et al., 2023), and offer the potential to increase cereal resilience to drought conditions (Kuerban et al., 2023; Lozano et al., 2022).

Despite the growing recognition of the importance of the microbiota for soil biochemical processes and plant growth and fitness in response to drought, harnessing these interactions for increased drought resilience remains a significant challenge due to complex interactions between the host plant and its surrounding soil influencing microbial community structure and function (Chen et al., 2019; Dong et al., 2023). A better mechanistic understanding of the complicated interactions in root-soil-microbiota associations is thereby needed to develop future strategies to predict and mitigate the impacts of drought on cereal yields and soil microbial functions. In this article, we will discuss how drought affects the dynamics of plant-microbiome interactions in cereal roots and present the importance of both sustainable agricultural practices and host genetics for potential root-based strategies to harness root-soil-microbiota interactions. Furthermore, root-derived mechanisms underlying microbiota assembly and the subsequent feedback of the microbiome to plant growth and fitness under drought conditions will be highlighted. Simultaneously, we will identify outstanding questions for future research and propose strategies to integrate microbiome information into soil manipulations and modern plant breeding programs, among others.

2. Drought affects the dynamics of root-microbiota interactions in cereals

Drought affects the dynamics of the microbiome associated with plants including changes in composition, ecology, and evolution of the microbiota (Fig. 1), which can influence microbial functions and the dynamics in agricultural settings. We elaborate on these individual aspects in the following sections.

2.1. Compositional changes in microbiota

Drought affects both bacterial and fungal microbiota associated with cereal plants. Drought impacts the composition of root-associated bacterial communities in a pattern that is strikingly conserved in different species of cereals (Naylor et al., 2017; Santos-Medellín et al., 2017). The primary hallmark is a near-universal enrichment of monoderm bacteria (Gram-positive) including *Actinobacteria*, and *Firmicutes*, and depletion of most diderm lineages (Gram-negative) (Breitkreuz et al., 2021; Fitzpatrick et al., 2018). Compared to bacteria, fungal communities such as Arbuscular Mycorrhizal fungi (AMF) are generally less affected by drought stress. Drought revealed no significant effects on root-associated fungal communities in some *Poaceae* species (Naylor et al., 2017; Salamon et al., 2020), whereas it significantly changed in rice (Andreo-jimenez et al., 2019), wheat (Azarbad et al., 2018; X. Wang et al., 2022), and maize (Lü et al. 2020). Nevertheless, several reports investigating the resistance and resilience of microbial communities to drought suggested that fungal communities, as compared to bacterial, were more resistant to drought but were less resilient (Gao et al., 2022; de Vries et al., 2018). Fungal communities are more resistant to drought due to their ability to form hyphal networks and due to their ability to form spores (Cheng et al., 2021). The higher resilience found in bacterial communities could reflect the fact that bacteria have a competitive

Fig. 1. Drought affects the dynamics of microbiota associated with cereal crops. While competitions between microbiota are intensified under No drought/rewetting conditions, resulting in the increased deterministic processes for bacterial assembly, stochastic processes dominate fungal and Gram-positive bacteria assembly under drought. An enrichment in Gram-positive bacteria such as *Actinobacteria* and *Firmicutes* and AMF species (e.g. *Glomeraceae*) and depletion of most Gram-negative taxa are observed under drought stress. In terms of microbial stability, fungal communities, as compared to bacteria, are more resistant to drought but are less resilient after rewetting due to their properties. Under intermittent drought, long-term adaptation implies the selection of these adapted microbial communities harboring beneficial functions after recurrent events to better tolerate subsequent drought, defined as drought legacy.

advantage at higher levels of moisture, including faster growth rates and better nutrient competition (Meisner et al., 2018). Gram-positive bacteria are also physiologically adapted to drought conditions. Gram-positive bacteria accumulate osmolytes, increasing their tolerance to osmotic stress under drought, and their cell wall properties also improve their drought tolerance by increasing their ability to resist desiccation and lipid peroxidation (Bremer and Krämer, 2019). Further, they may gain a competitive growth advantage over other soil microbes under low nutrition availability conditions during water limitations. For example, increased activity of ATP-binding cassette transporter genes (Xu et al., 2018) and iron transport and metabolism functionality (Xu et al., 2021b) are correlated with these shifts in the community composition of cereals. The fact that Gram-positive bacteria and AMF enrich higher in the rhizosphere and roots than in bulk soil in response to drought, indicates that the enrichment of drought-induced microbiota is at least partly driven by interactions with the plant host (Simmons et al., 2020). Several proposed molecular mechanisms including shifts in plant metabolism, plant root exudates, and plant immune responses would likely affect microbial communities under drought (Xu and Coleman-Derr, 2019). Hence, the complex interactions between host and microbial traits may influence the microbial community structure under drought stress.

2.2. Eco-evolutional changes in microbiota

Both fungal and bacterial communities associated with different compartments of cereals were governed primarily by ecological drift in response to drought (Gao et al., 2020; Xie et al., 2021). However, there is some evidence showing that altered community composition and assembly can be associated with functional changes in microbiota. For example, Gao et al. (2022) showed that the co-occurrence networks among functional guilds of fungal communities in sorghum roots were strengthened by drought. Fungal lineages enhance water uptake and nutrient acquisition under drought stress (Jerbi et al., 2022; Quiroga et al., 2018). They also have a protective effect on bacterial communities exposed to drought (Hestrin et al., 2022; Imran et al., 2023), indicating that fungal-bacterial interactions can support bacterial communities in drought conditions. Microbial gene expression patterns are rapidly modified by changing relative abundances of community members or through mechanisms such as horizontal gene transfer (Zilber-Rosenberg and Rosenberg, 2021), offering fast and agile responses to drought stress (Pande et al., 2023). Microbial modulation of drought stress-resistant genes such as aquaporins (Symanczik et al., 2020), antioxidants (Murli et al., 2021), transcription factors (Manjunatha et al., 2022; Paul et al., 2022), proline biosynthesis (Govindasamy et al., 2020), modulation of epigenetic responses (Lephatsi et al., 2022), and modulation of plant hormones (Ojuederie and Babalola, 2023) enhance drought tolerance and plant growth in cereals.

Drought can cause evolutionary effects on soil microbiome known as legacy effects, whereby soil communities continue to show signatures of drought for many years and even modify microbial responses to later drought events (Müller and Bahn, 2022). The drought legacy in soil microbiota can affect the microorganisms associated with the rhizosphere and root endosphere of cereal plants and can affect biomass, fitness, and root traits in drought-stressed cereals (Carter et al., 2023; Gebauer et al., 2022; Santos-medellín et al., 2021). For example, wheat plants had higher root biomass when grown in soil with a history of water stress (Azarbad et al., 2018). Drought legacy resulted in enduring impacts on rice root microbiomes and contributed to the host response to drought (Santos-Medellín et al., 2021). Maize plants inoculated with a microbiota from a water-limited legacy soil were more tolerant to drought by producing longer roots and generating more organic carbon in the soil, potentially stimulating the microbiome, and slowing soil water loss during drought (Carter et al., 2023). Further, the drought history affects microbial population dynamics and functions such as enzyme activities involved in carbon, nitrogen, and phosphorus cycling,

which can, in turn, affect the plant's nutrition status and fitness and overall soil fertility (Canarini et al., 2021; Kelly et al., 2023). It has recently been suggested that the prolonged drought through drying-rewetting cycles can help to select generalists adapted to both drought and non-drought conditions and that harbor a larger repertoire of genes beneficial for plant growth and development under drought (Schmidt et al., 2023). However, whether and how controlled drought stress followed by strategic rewetting can be employed for cereal production in regions with limited sources of water deserves further investigation.

On the other hand, the preceding plant can also leave legacies in soil microbial communities which can influence the response of soil microorganisms to a subsequent drought and the growth of the following plant (Jochum et al., 2019; Kuerban et al., 2023). Host plants can memorize drought events through epigenetic regulation of gene transcription for a robust response to the following droughts (Sadhukhan et al., 2022). The plant 'memory' could further contribute to the legacy effects on plant microbiota through changes in root exudation and root morphology (Lozano et al., 2022; de Vries et al., 2023). Changes in soil communities in response to altered root exudation patterns can lead to increased nutrient availability after drought, possibly leading to improved plant growth (de Vries et al., 2019). Therefore, unlike resistance and resilience which concerns rapid responses to drought, long-term adaptation to drought implies the selection of adapted microbial communities and host plant genes harboring beneficial functions after recurrent stress events to better tolerate subsequent drought.

3. Selection-driven approaches to harness root-soil-microbiota interactions under drought

3.1. Sustainable agricultural practices for the selection of microbes

Plants recruit root microbial communities from their surrounding soils, and soil characteristics such as soil nutrients (Finkel et al., 2019), pH (Schlatte et al., 2020), organic matter (Wu et al., 2022), texture (Yim et al., 2022), and other soil-related features are among the dominant drivers of microbial community structure in cropping systems of cereals. Drought stress regulating substrate availability and soil structure properties presents distinct microbial community composition and their overall activity and function in soil (Naylor et al., 2023; Tripathi et al., 2017). Nevertheless, the impact of drought stress on soil microorganisms and their functions depends on the soil organic carbon; higher soil organic matter contents have shown a lower susceptibility in microbial compositions under drought (Moore et al., 2023; Siebielec et al., 2020). The addition of organic amendments, which is a strategy employed on agricultural land, can thereby impact the soil microbiome. Organic amendments can confer stability against drought on the soil microbiome (Sun et al., 2023b). Bacterial diversity was higher with organic than with chemical fertilization in drought-stressed soils, and the use of organic fertilizer showed a higher recovery of bacterial communities after rewetting (Sun et al., 2023b), supporting that organic amendments can improve microbial drought resilience. Similarly, organic-amended soils have greater effects on the microbiome network complexity, the stability of microbial functions, soil nutrients, and crop productivity in maize (Durrer et al., 2021; Yan et al., 2023). Soil organic practices can also affect the stability of legacy effects under drought (Gebauer et al., 2022; Moore et al., 2023). The rhizosphere of wheat plants grown in organic amended soils contained higher amounts of total nitrogen, potassium, and phosphorus compared to inorganic fertilizer and control (Amadou et al., 2020; Kavamura et al., 2018). In maize and rice, the application of organic fertilizer also changes soil keystone taxa significantly correlating with functional genes related to the carbon and nitrogen cycles, and increases drought tolerance and yield (Renwick et al., 2021; Sun et al., 2023a). These studies suggest that organic amendments confer microbial diversity, stability, and function to the soil promoting plant performance under drought conditions.

In addition to organic fertilizer, other sustainable agricultural management such as conservation tillage (Banerjee et al., 2019; Han et al., 2024), intercropping (Pambuka et al., 2022; Pivato et al., 2021; Singh and Mathimaran, 2019), and crop rotation (Oberholster et al., 2018) may also support more complex and beneficial rhizosphere microbial networks and can affect ecosystem functioning in the soil such as soil aggregation, and carbon and nitrogen processes under drought. For example, intercropping enhanced organic carbon and nitrogen concentrations in soil aggregates (Peng et al., 2023). By sharing the necessary phenotypes for e.g. nitrogen fixation or tolerance to drought, an intercropping system including legumes and cereals can positively affect the composition of root microbial communities under water stress (Singh and Mathimaran, 2019). Legume-based rotations can have clear economic advantages over cereal monocropping in dry lands by enhancing soil nitrogen, and phosphorus availability, by supporting favorable microbial communities in the rhizosphere, and breaking soil-borne disease cycles (Yigezu et al., 2019). Crop rotation diversification also enhances maize drought resistance (Renwick et al., 2021). Further, long-term conservation tillage can impact soil aggregates by increasing carbon content and enzyme activity, thereby modifying the soil microbial community composition within aggregate size fractions in semiarid agroecosystems (Han et al., 2024). However, there are contradictory results related to the impact of agricultural practices on the cereal root microbiome. For example, in one study, none of the agricultural practices including tillage and crop rotation affected the diversity and composition of rhizosphere bacterial communities associated with wheat roots (Lupwayi et al., 2021). Interacting or synergistic effects of agricultural practices including biotic and abiotic factors (e.g. plant genotype, soil characteristics, drought- and plant-driven legacies) on microbiome structure and function may be a probable reason for the high variability in results. A large volume of meta-analysis studies has been undertaken to evaluate the effects of different agricultural practices on soil bacterial and fungal communities and showed that the long term management practices based on sustainability can improve soil quality and ultimately support functionally diverse microbiomes in crops (Christel, Maron, and Ranjard, 2021; Kim et al., 2020), hence can be considered for harnessing soil microbiome under water scarcity.

3.2. Host genetics for selection of microbes

Under drought, the host genotype is responsible for some of the variation in the root-associated microbiomes of rice (Andreo-jimenez et al., 2019; Li et al., 2023), wheat (Azarbad et al., 2020; Si et al., 2021; Žiarovsk et al., 2020), barley (Sendek et al., 2019), and maize (Guevara-hernandez et al., 2024). A study on the soil microbiome in rice fields determined microbial composition shifts in response to drought and the presence of host plants (Jang et al., 2020). In a study by Naylor et al. (2017), up to 20% variance of microbial communities was observed within different cereal species such as sorghum, maize, barley, and wheat under drought. These results indicate that the host genetic factor at the species but also cultivar level is an important determinant in shaping root microbiomes. Examining drought-stressed genotypes showed higher microbial species richness under water deficit and indicated that drought-tolerant cultivars exert a stronger selection on microbial communities in the face of drought conditions (Azarbad et al., 2022; Gaete et al., 2021; Kristy et al., 2022).

Conditions in which domesticated plants are typically grown can influence their microbial communities, and the plant-associated microbiomes of domesticated cereals are different in comparison to their ancestors and wild varieties (Abera et al., 2022; Gholizadeh et al., 2022). Under drought conditions, wild plants exerted a strong effect on root microbiome assembly in rice (Aparna and Nunna, 2022; Ding et al., 2020; Xie et al., 2021). In a report by Aparna and Nunna (2022), a rice landrace recruited a specific group of microorganisms during drought, potentially maintaining its rhizosphere functioning related to soil carbon pool, enzyme activity, and respiration. Characterizing the root

mycobiome of wild and domesticated pearl millet grown in arid and semi-arid areas, Mofini et al. (2022) showed a higher relative abundance of saprotrophic fungal species in the wild millet. It suggests that wild plants probably provide a more appropriate ecological niche for saprotrophic fungi under water deficit, and could benefit from mineralization of nutrients driven by saprotrophs. Similarly, Favela et al. (2021) illustrated that more recently developed maize germplasms recruit fewer microbial taxa with the genetic capability for sustainable nitrogen provisioning and larger populations of microorganisms that contribute to nitrogen losses. Most modern cereals are the result of intensive selective breeding to maximize yields, leading to the potential loss of some of the genetic traits needed to recruit microbiota (Raaijmakers and Kiers, 2022). Therefore, wild and semi-domesticated genotypes such as landraces can hold great genetic potential for harnessing root-soil-microbiota interactions in cereals. By identifying sources of variation in root traits between cereals and their wild relatives, researchers can learn how this variation may offer opportunities for plant breeders to develop the next generation of cereals optimized for root-soil-microbiota associations. The aspects of the identification of the root traits and manipulation of the host genetic factors for improved recruitment of microbiota will be discussed in the following sections.

4. Plant-microbiome communication and the subsequent feedback on plant fitness under drought

In the following we will review the plant-derived mechanisms underlying microbiome assembly, focusing on the role of root traits including root architectural and morphological traits, root exudates, and plant immune system in maintaining microbiome structure and function, and the subsequent feedback to plant growth and fitness under drought conditions.

4.1. Bidirectional interactions between plant metabolites and microbiome under drought

Root exudates can facilitate water and nutrient acquisition (Sindhu et al., 2022; Wen et al., 2021), microbiome selection (Zhalnina et al., 2018), and can help plants cope with drought stress (Chai and Schachtman, 2022). Under mild drought conditions, the biomass allocation into roots increases (Wach and Skowron, 2022), and root exudation is usually higher than that of well-watered controls (Tiziani et al., 2022). Specifically, drought increased the abundance of organic acids exuded by maize (Song et al., 2012), wheat (Anderson et al., 2023), and pearl millet (Ghatak et al., 2022). Drought also increases the concentration of secondary metabolites in various plants (Gargallo-garriga et al., 2018; Ghatak et al., 2022; He et al., 2022). Comparative metabolic profiling of the root primary and secondary exudates of pearl millet under drought showed an enhancement in the concentration of organic acids, water-soluble vitamins, plant hormones, and several phenolic compounds (Ghatak et al., 2022). Gargallo-garriga et al. (Gargallo-garriga et al., 2018) also revealed an increased synthesis of secondary metabolites such as alkaloids and terpenoids in root exudates of holm oak under drought. After drought recovery, however, exudates were dominated by primary metabolites and changes in root exudate composition were irreversible under extreme drought. This observation suggests that the effect of root exudates may be context-dependent (Williams and de Vries, 2020). The functional implications of drought-induced changes in the quantity and quality of root exudates have further been assessed by de Vries et al. (2019). They found that root exudates from drought-stressed plants can potentially influence soil carbon cycling through the decomposition of soil carbon, an evolutionary strategy in plants to deal with adverse effects of drought stress through the stimulation of microbial activity and the subsequent mineralization of nutrients in the soil and plant regrowth, indicating the importance of root exudates for both soil fertility and plant fitness under drought.

The composition of exudates impacts rhizosphere microbial communities (Seitz et al., 2022). Under drought, plant-microbiome interactions appear to be largely modulated by root exudates as observed in sorghum (Caddell et al., 2023), maize (Tiziani et al., 2022), rice (Li et al., 2023), and wheat (Anderson et al., 2023). The decrease in community diversity and increase in relative abundance of drought-induced lineages correlated with specific modulation in amino acids and carbohydrate exudations in these studies. Secondary metabolites like phenolic compounds are also involved in root-microbiome interactions in cereals (Balasubramanian et al., 2021; Tiziani et al., 2022). Root endosphere and rhizosphere microbiomes of maize were modulated by benzoxazinoid compounds (P. Wang et al., 2022). Strigolactones also served as signals for a symbiosis of plants with root-associated microbiomes in rice (Kim et al., 2022). Evidence highlights a positive correlation between strigolactones and AMF colonization in plants under drought (Carvalho et al., 2019; Ruiz-Lozano et al., 2016), with increased AMF abundance potentially facilitating increased tolerance to drought stress (Ruiz-Lozano et al., 2016). The studies support the notion that root exudates facilitate direct communication between plants and microbes and act as signaling molecules to recruit root microbiomes. How these drought-enriched exudates configure root microbiome composition to promote plant stress responses remains to be determined.

There is a growing body of evidence showing that some plant-associated microbes facilitate drought resistance in cereals by increasing the abundance of several primary and secondary metabolites (Table 1). Primary metabolites play critical roles in maintaining cellular integrity, osmotic adjustment, and energy production under drought conditions (Ali et al., 2022). Accumulation of sugars, organic acids, amino acids, and fatty acids is differentially regulated in various cereals inoculated by different microbes under drought (El-daim et al., 2019; Ghaffari et al., 2019; Hu et al., 2020). AMF-primed wheat plants revealed a differential accumulation of primary and secondary metabolites including lipids, flavonoids (flavone and flavanol), carbohydrates, sulfur-containing compounds, terpenoids, amino acids, and antioxidants under drought (Bernardo et al., 2019; Tereucán et al., 2021). In maize, the application of a consortium of Bacilli strains led to differential changes in the profiles of amino acid, TCA intermediates, hormones, flavonoid, and phenolic compounds, steviol glycosides, and oxylipins in response to water deficit (Lephatsi et al., 2022; Othibeng et al., 2022). Polyphenols and flavonoids also increased due to AMF inoculation under both medium drought and severe drought stress in barley (Jerbi et al., 2022). Plant secondary metabolites are involved in stress response and defense mechanisms. For instance, these compounds help scavenge reactive oxygen species (ROS) generated during stress, protect cellular structures from oxidative damage, and regulate various signaling pathways involved in stress response (Yadav et al., 2021). For instance, in rice grown under drought conditions, an endophytic fungi *Aspergillus fumigatus* effectively alleviated the harm by regulating the contents of NADPH oxidases, antioxidants, and heat shock proteins, all of which are closely related to the ROS pathway (Qin et al., 2019). The microbe-induced reprogramming in plant metabolites is thereby required for cereal tolerance to drought stress (Bernardo et al., 2019; Tereucán et al., 2021). Microbial-induced shifts in pathways related to hormonal signaling (Carlson et al., 2020; Lephatsi et al., 2022) and gene expression (Barnawal et al., 2017; Manjunatha et al., 2022) possibly contribute to the drought-resistance responses in cereals.

4.2. Root architectural traits and microbiota interaction under drought stress

Root architectural and morphological traits such as root length, lateral root number, root surface area, branching angle, root density, root diameter, root hairs, and root cell wall thickness are among root traits mediating drought tolerance in plants (Shoab et al., 2022). Deep rooting, lateral root number, root length density, and root surface area aid in water and nutrient uptake from water-limited soils (Siddiqui et al.,

2021). Plants change their root phenotypic traits in response to drought, soil texture, and other factors; for instance, longer roots can access water from deeper layers of soil during water-limited stress (Shoab et al., 2022). Nevertheless, many distinct host genes control the plasticity in response to water deficit (Schneider et al., 2020), posing a challenge in breeding programs for root architecture. Further, breeding for deeper rooting systems for increasing drought tolerance is associated with a metabolic cost for the plants; otherwise, the plant would invest more in shoot and aboveground biomass. This has led to an increasing interest in altering root phenotypes for greater metabolic efficiency.

Root-soil interfaces show a large contribution to drought adaptation and root plasticity through the interactions between root traits and microbiota (Hallett et al., 2022). Root morphological traits are mediators of beneficial plant-microbe interactions, and several studies have revealed that root traits such as specific root length, root angle, root diameter, root hair, lateral root branching density, and endodermal cell wall influence the rhizosphere microbiome assembly and function in wheat (Kavamura et al., 2020) and maize (Galindo-castañeda et al., 2022; Galindo-Castañeda et al., 2019; Szoboszlay et al., 2015). Similarly, root phenotypic variables such as specific root length are a major driver of root exudation and can affect microbial communities and enzymatic activities in soil under normal and drought conditions (Meier et al., 2020; de Vries et al., 2016). It is speculated that root systems with longer roots have thinner roots, and the carbon costs of root construction are reduced, indicating more carbon may be available for root exudation, which can lead to a change in soil microbial communities and enzyme activities (Meier et al., 2020).

Among a wide range of root attributes participating in the higher specific root length, particular attention has been focused on root hairs. Root hairs have received more interest due to their roles in soil penetration, nutrient and water uptake, root exudation, rhizosheath formation, and interactions with beneficial soil microorganisms (Rongsawat et al., 2020). Root hairs have relatively short lifespans, high turnover rates, and have the capacity to increase belowground carbon cycling (Acharya et al., 2023; Holz et al., 2018). For example, the amount of exuded carbon in barley roots from a hairless mutant was three times lower (Holz et al., 2018). This indicates that root hairs increase rhizosphere extension and carbon input into soils. Higher carbon, nitrogen, and phosphorus cycle enzyme activity in plant roots is linked to root hairs (Bilyera et al., 2021; Ma et al., 2018; Zhang et al., 2020a), reflecting increased root exudation and microbial activity. Similarly, the presence and function of root hairs were a determinant of bacterial communities in barley (Robertson-Albertyn et al., 2017) and maize (Gebauer et al., 2021; Ruger et al., 2023). Root hairs harbor higher bacterial diversity and plants with relatively more root hairs recruit more diverse microbial communities (Lozano et al., 2022; Spor et al., 2020). The presence of root hairs further mitigates the negative impacts of drought on roots and microorganisms by increasing root exudation and boosting enzyme activities (Zhang et al., 2023). Moreover, root hairs, together with fungal hyphae, and microbial and plant-derived adhesive agents, are important for rhizosheath formation in cereals (Chai and Schachtman, 2022; Galloway et al., 2020). The higher moisture and nutrient contents of rhizosheath create favorable niches for colonization by microorganisms, which ultimately improve the overall fitness of cereals under drought (Basirat et al., 2019; Liu et al., 2019; Rabbi et al., 2022).

The effect of root hairs on the microbiome depends on physical barriers such as soil texture (e.g. loam vs sand) (Yim et al., 2022) and plant anatomical characteristics such as endodermis and cell wall structure (Salas-gonzález et al., 2021; Verbon et al., 2023). The Casparian strip constitutes a physical diffusion barrier to water and nutrients in plant roots, which is formed by the polar deposition of lignin polymer in the endodermis tissue. It has previously been observed that mutants displaying defects in suberin deposition in the Casparian strip displayed perturbations in both root exudates and microbiome composition (Durr et al., 2021). Given that lignified cells may restrict the

Table 1
Effect of microbe(s) inoculations on cereal metabolites under drought in selected literature.

Cereal plant	Microbe/s	Effect on cereal hosts' metabolites	Role of metabolites	Reference
Wheat (<i>Triticum</i> spp.)	<i>Funneliformis mosseae</i>	Changes in levels of lipids, flavonoids, carbohydrates, sulfur compounds, terpenoids, amino acids, and hormones (BR, GA, ABA)	Modulation of oxidative stress	(Bernardo et al. 2019)
	<i>Glomus mosseae</i>	Changes in levels of proteins related to sugar metabolism, cell wall rearrangement, cytoskeletal organization, plant stress responses, and JA biosynthesis	Reducing the osmotic stress and maintaining cellular integrity	(Bernardo et al. 2017)
	<i>Funneliformis mosseae</i> or <i>Claroideoglomus claroideum</i>	Increased flavonoid (apigenin and luteolin) and antioxidant activity	Modulation of oxidative stress	(Tereucán et al. 2021)
	<i>Pseudomonas chlororaphis</i> isolate O6	Changes in levels of amino acids, low molecular weight organic acids, phenolic acids, and siderophore	Potential impacts on plant vigor and metal bioavailability	(Anderson et al. 2023)
	<i>Bacillus velezensis</i> 5113	Changes in gene expression and metabolites involved in the TCA cycle and the synthesis of amino acids (arginine and proline), amino sugars, and carbohydrates	Supporting both growth and stress management	(El-daim et al. 2019)
	<i>Epichloë</i> endophytes	Changes in levels of proline, ABA, JA, and phenolic compounds	Modulation of physiological responses to water-limited conditions	(Llorens et al. 2019)
	<i>Arthrobacter protophormiae</i> , or <i>Dietzia natronolimnaea</i> , or <i>Bacillus subtilis</i> <i>Streptomyces pactum</i> Act12	Regulation of indigenous levels of ABA, IAA, ET, and enhanced expressions of the CTR1 and DREB2 genes Increased levels of ABA and the expression levels of EXPA2, EXPA6, P5CS, and SnRK2	Improving the tolerance of plants to abiotic stress Enhancing the osmotic adjustment and antioxidant capacity	(Barnawal et al. 2017) (Li et al. 2020)
Maize (<i>Zea mays</i>)	Consortium of <i>Bacilli</i> including <i>Bacillus licheniformis</i> , <i>Brevibacillus leterosporus</i> , and <i>Bacillus amyloliquefaciens</i>	Different levels of amino acids, phytohormones, flavonoids, and phenolic acids, gene expression, and global DNA methylation profiles	Increased biomass and enzymatic regulators of oxidative stress	(Lephatsi et al. 2022)
	Consortium of <i>Bacilli</i> including <i>Bacillus licheniformis</i> , <i>Brevibacillus leterosporus</i> , and <i>Bacillus amyloliquefaciens</i>	Changes in levels of amino acids, hormones (IAA, ABA, ET, SA), TCA intermediates, phenolics, steviol glycosides and oxylipins	Growth promotion and enhanced defenses	(Othibeng et al. 2022)
	<i>Azospirillum brasilense</i> SP-7 or <i>Herbaspirillum seropedicae</i> Z-152	Lower levels of ABA and ET and gene expression of ZmVP14 are involved in the synthesis of ABA.	Growth promotion and enhanced stress response	(Curá et al. 2017)
	<i>Rhizophagus irregularis</i>	Increased levels of fatty acid- and ornithine cycle-related metabolites along with soluble sugars, putrescine, and γ -aminobutyric acid (GABA)	Increased growth performance	(Hu et al. 2020)
	<i>Funneliformis mosseae</i>	Increased levels of phenols and antioxidant enzyme activity	Supporting growth and nutrient uptake	(Bahraminia et al. 2020)
	Consortium of <i>Bacilli</i> including <i>Bacillus licheniformis</i> , <i>Brevibacillus laterosporus</i> , and <i>Bacillus amyloliquefaciens</i> .	Increased levels of phenolics, lipids, amino acids, hormones (ABA and zeatin), and organic acids	Supporting redox homeostasis, strengthening of the plant cell wall, osmoregulation, energy production, and membrane remodeling	(Nephali et al. 2021)
	<i>Rhizophagus irregularis</i> , EEZ 58	Regulation of aquaporin genes	Water homeostasis or transport of other solutes	(Quiroga et al. 2017)
	<i>Rhizophagus irregularis</i> EEZ 58	Modulation of hydraulic conductivity, gene expression of aquaporins (PIP2;4 and TIP1;1), and endogenous levels of SA, ABA, and JA	Modulation of plant water relations	(Quiroga et al. 2018)
	<i>Piriformospora indica</i>	Stimulated genes for hormone functions, including those that respond to ABA, auxin, SA, and CK such as TGA1/4/9/10 and ARR2/9	Supporting growth promotion and drought tolerance	(Zhang et al. 2018)
	<i>Piriformospora indica</i>	Up-regulation of drought-related genes DREB2A, CBL1, ANAC072, and RD29A	Plant protection against the detrimental effects of drought	(Xu et al. 2017)
Barley (<i>Hordeum vulgare</i>)	<i>Piriformospora indica</i>	Regulating amino acid and soluble sugar metabolism, ABC transporters for TCA intermediates, a hexose and sucrose transporter, and autophagy-related proteins (EXO70B1, Exo70F1)	Mitigation of damage caused by oxidative stress	(Ghaffari et al. 2019)
	Consortia of five AMF species	Increased fatty acid contents (C18:0 and C18:1), total contents of polyphenol and flavonoid, the mineral content of gains (K, Cu, Fe, Zn, and Ca)	Enhanced the water tolerance resulting in higher grain yield and quality	(Jerbi et al. 2022)
Sorghum (<i>Sorghum bicolor</i>)	<i>Glomus mosseae</i> + Nitroxin (<i>Azospirillum</i> sp. and <i>Azotobacter rhizobacteria</i>)	Increased levels of anthocyanin, carotenoid, flavonoid, and IAA	Supporting physiological and biochemical traits grain yield and protein content	(Kamali and Mehraban, 2020)
	<i>Bacillus</i> sp. and <i>Pseudomonas</i> sp.	Increased contents of flavonoids, flavone, ubiquinone, terpenoid quinone, amino acids, osmolytes, hormones, and alpha-linolenic acid metabolism	Enhanced drought stress tolerance through antioxidant capacity, root architecture modification, and induced systemic tolerance	(Carlson et al. 2020)
	<i>Rhizophagus irregularis</i> or <i>Rhizophagus arabicus</i>	Regulation of major intrinsic proteins such as different PIPs	Modulation of water homeostasis	(Symanczik et al. 2020)
	<i>Ochrobactrum</i> sp. EB-165, or <i>Microbacterium</i> sp. EB-65, or <i>Enterobacter</i> sp. EB-14, or <i>Enterobacter cloacae</i> EB-48	Up-regulation of drought-responsive genes like sbP5CS2 and sbP5CS1	Contributing to plant growth promotion as well as induced stress tolerance	(Govindasamy et al. 2020)
Pearl millet (<i>Pennisetum glaucum</i>)	<i>Shewanella putrefaciens</i> MCL-1 and <i>Cronobacter dublinensis</i> MKS-1	Increased contents of ABA, GA, IAA, and expression level of genes involved in phytohormone biosynthesis (NCED, GA20ox, and SBYUC) and	Modulating root growth, plant hormones, physiology, and drought tolerance	(Manjunatha et al. 2022)

(continued on next page)

Table 1 (continued)

Cereal plant	Microbe/s	Effect on cereal hosts' metabolites	Role of metabolites	Reference
		drought-responsive transcription factors (AP2, SNAC1, and DREB2A)		
	<i>Bacillus amyloliquefaciens</i>	Relative expression of drought-responsive marker genes (DREB-1E and ERF-1B), and an increase in the relative expression of APX1 and SOD1	Supporting plants against drought through the antioxidant system	(Murali et al. 2021)
Rice (<i>Oryza sativa</i>)	Consortium of <i>Bacillus amyloliquefaciens</i> Bk7 and <i>Brevibacillus laterosporus</i> B4	Increased expression of MYB3R-2, DIL, DREB1A and CDPK13 genes	Drought tolerance through an increased antioxidant activity	(Kakar et al. 2016)
	<i>Aspergillus fumigatus</i> SG-17	Regulating the contents of NADPH oxidases, antioxidants, and heat shock proteins through a coumarin analog NFA	Regulating the oxidative pathway	(Qin et al. 2019)

passage of solutes, organic compounds, and microorganisms between inner cell layers in roots, it has been proposed that the degree of lignification in root cell walls might be correlated to microbial colonization of maize plants (Galindo-castañeda et al., 2022). Reciprocally, Salas-González et al. (Salas-gonzález et al., 2021) illustrated that the inoculation with a synthetic community (SynCom) consisting of 41 taxonomically diverse bacteria repressed the expression of genes related to cell wall lignification through an ABA-dependent pathway. Using this observation, along with data on nutrient contents, the authors suggest that the activity of the root bacterial community and the diffusion barriers can balance nutrient status in plants, thereby leading to stress tolerance. Downregulation of genes associated with endodermal barriers and cell wall biogenesis facilitated microbiome assembly (Salas-gonzález et al., 2021; Verbon et al., 2023) as well as microbiome-driven architectural changes in root hairs (Verbon et al., 2023). These observations will probably affect conceptual models for root plasticity in response to drought, in which more focus will be on increasing hair roots as well as optimizing of cell wall lignification and root length to harness the root-soil-microbiota interactions for drought resilient crops.

Interactions between plant roots and mutualistic soil bacteria and fungi lead to profound modifications of root architecture (Grover et al., 2021; Ma et al., 2021) influencing root system functioning under drought (Araújo et al., 2023; Ojuederie and Babalola, 2023). For example, a meta-analysis study showed that drought alleviation emancipated by AMF is mediated by root trait modification and phosphorous acquisition efficacy (Chandrasekaran, 2022). Auxin-producing microbes coordinate indigenous root auxins leading to an increase in root fresh weight, rhizosheath formation, and water use efficiency in drought-stressed rice seedlings (Xu et al., 2021a). Auxins modulate root elongation and induce lateral root formation, and indeed, microbes may alter root systems by either producing auxins (Raheem et al., 2018) or inducing plant genes involved in auxin production (Manjunatha et al., 2022). The phytohormone ABA can also promote root hair elongation and crosstalk with auxin biosynthesis observed in rice (Wang et al., 2017) and barley (Zhang et al., 2021). The effect of the plant hormone ethylene (ET) on root growth is also largely mediated through interactions with auxin, via the regulation of auxin biosynthesis or local auxin distribution, and increased ET levels essentially lead to the inhibition of root elongation and production of root hairs (M. Li et al., 2022). In this context, some bacteria deaminate the precursor of ET, 1-aminocyclopropane-1-carboxylate (ACC), and the ACC deaminase activity lowers ET levels and alleviates the repressive effect of ET on root elongation leading to improved nutrient acquisition and water uptake capacity (Zarei et al., 2020), and supports cereal growth under drought (Ojuederie and Babalola, 2023; Umapathi et al., 2022).

4.3. Complex interplay between plant immunity and microbiome under drought

The plant's innate immune system primarily involves the perception of microbe- or pathogen-associated molecular patterns (MAMPs or

PAMPs) by individual effector proteins through nucleotide-binding leucine-rich repeat (NLR) immune receptors. This leads to MAMP- or PAMP-triggered immunity (MTI or PTI) and effector-triggered immunity (ETI), respectively (Teixeira et al., 2019). These two layers of the plant immune system (MTI/PTI and ETI) have been proposed to play key roles not only in triggering plant responses against pathogens but also in establishing and maintaining plant microbiota homeostasis (Horton et al., 2014; Lebeis et al., 2015). Recently, Ruger et al. (Ruger et al., 2023) identified significant correlations between microbial taxa associated with the maize roots and gene expression patterns involved in plant immunity such as response to JA, systemic acquired resistance, and phenylpropanoid biosynthetic process. Research in cereal plants such as rice (Santos-Medellin et al., 2022), millet (Y. Wang et al., 2022), and barley (Escudero-martinez et al., 2022) have shown that the transcriptional reprogramming in response to the associated microbiota reduces the expression of a large fraction of LRRs and NLRs in plant roots inoculated with microbiomes. Similarly, plant immunity is in part responsible for regulating the establishment of the root microbiome of cereals under drought (Caddell et al., 2023; Wang et al., 2021; Zhang et al., 2020b). Differentially expressed genes related to MTI/PTI, ETI, and downstream defense responses including calcium burst, activation of mitogen-activated protein kinases (MAPKs), and ET-related pathways are regulated in rice root under moderate drought stress, and associated with rhizosheath formation (Wang et al., 2021; Zhang et al., 2020b). The evidence supports the idea that plants may reduce their immune response under drought, leading to changes in microbiota composition such as colonization by beneficial microbes. The regulatory relationship between plant hormones presenting the plant growth and development under drought stress and the plant immune system can also affect the microbial communities in plant roots (Li et al., 2023; S. Li et al., 2022). Under drought, ABA is produced in roots to induce stomatal closure in the leaves (Hsu et al., 2021). Drought-induced ABA acts antagonistically on SA-mediated immune signaling (Yasuda et al., 2008), indicating that roots may benefit from being less immune-sensitive during drought conditions. Although the effect of root-produced ABA on the root microbiota has yet to be determined, ABA is known to activate plant genes for the production of reactive oxygen species (ROS) in the apoplast (Voothuluru et al., 2020), where most bacterial endophytes reside. The impact of the plant immune system on the microbiome through ROS signaling has previously been proposed (Pfeilmeier et al., 2021; Song et al., 2021). However, whether ROS and/or ABA affect the drought-stressed root microbiome deserves further investigation.

The plant microbiome functions as an additional component of the plant immune system and can reduce the outbreak of plant diseases directly via microbe-microbe interactions or indirectly via stimulation of plant immunity suggested in different cereals such as barley (Mahdi et al., 2022), and maize (Shao et al., 2023). Nevertheless, drought modulates plant immunity through several mechanisms, which can affect the plant-associated microbiota and its response to pathogens. First, environmental factors can directly modulate the expression of plant immune outputs (Huot et al., 2017; Janda et al., 2019). Further, hormonal regulators of plant responses to drought stress can have an

antagonistic effect on plant immunity through the suppression of the defense pathways. For example, changes in levels of the plant hormones ABA and SA during drought can lead to suppression of the immune response through the SA signaling pathway in mesophyll cells, thus compromising SA-mediated resistance in the leaf (Mine et al., 2017). Finally, shared signaling components can jointly coordinate plant responses to biotic and abiotic stressors (Espinoza et al., 2017). Regarding growth and immunity trade-offs, the prioritization of microbiota-induced growth in the context of drought stress can be associated with downregulation of microbiota-induced defense responses, putting plants at the risk of pathogens. However, microbial inoculants in wheat promoted plant growth under salt stress and improved disease resistance by activating immune pathway-related genes such as *WRKY* and *ERF* in roots and leaves (Ji et al., 2023).

Evidence also points to a scenario in which plants and rhizosphere bacterial communities combine to trigger the production of scopoletin with selective antimicrobial activity in a *MYB72-BGLU42* dependent manner, that can shape the root-associated microbiota resulting in improved immunity against pathogens (Stringlis et al., 2018). There is an intriguing possibility that the different bacterial communities in younger versus older leaves are adapted to contribute preferentially to biotic or abiotic tolerance, respectively (Berens et al., 2019). Moreover, bacterial and fungal communities of the plant leaves are modulated by belowground communities of AMF and soil nutrients under drought, resulting in the resistance of leaf communities to invasion by the foliar pathogen *Pseudomonas syringae* (Debray et al., 2022). These studies indicate that plant growth and defense responses are involved in distinct feedback loops with the plant microbiota, influencing resource

Fig. 2. Schematic representation of complex interactions between root-based traits, soil characteristics, and microbiome and some selection-driven strategies for harnessing the complexity of root-soil-microbiota associations. Different host traits including root exudates, root architectural and morphological traits, and plant immune systems interact not only with each other but also with soil properties (e.g. soil organic matter, soil texture, soil nutrients, and soil pH), host factors (e.g. host genetics, physiology), and drought stress (e.g. intensity, duration, and frequency) exerting a significant effect on the root microbial diversity, activity, legacy, and function with consequences for soil carbon and nutrient cycling as well as plant resilience and fitness in water-limited conditions. Considering the complicated interplay between these multipartite associations, it is conceivable that optimizing the interactions can modulate plasticity for both aboveground and belowground tissues for greater metabolic efficiency. Using such an optimizing approach, the interactions between the root-based traits should be harnessed to provide more resilient genotypes for drought, with the altered attitude that more is not always better. Since plants have a limited quantity of energy, the allocation of limited carbon sources to root-based traits is consequently influenced by growth-defense trade-offs. This suggests that only under equilibrium between root traits more resilient genotypes should be obtained through modern breeding and engineering programs for host genome manipulation. Further, selection, design, and application of SynComs as well as sustainable agricultural practices such as organic amendment and divers cropping systems (e.g. legume-cereal based types) represent soil manipulation approaches to improve cereal plasticity and resilience for drought stress, hence can be considered for harnessing root-soil-microbiota under water scarcity. A combination of different approaches should cooperate to attain productivity in cereals in response to drought stress.

investment strategies and promoting plant fitness in response to both biotic and abiotic stresses. Therefore, when plants are challenged by pathogens under water limitation, mutualistic symbioses have the potential to enhance plant growth and defense, however, it may be context-dependent, and vary depending on factors such as host plants, leaf age, soil nutrients, and the belowground microbiome, among other factors, which need further investigation. A schematic representation of complex interactions between root-based traits, soil characteristics, and microbiome is shown in Fig. 2.

5. Manipulations of the root-soil-microbiota interactions for drought-resilient cereals

By implementing several strategies to manipulate the soils and host plants, farmers can create agricultural settings that are more sustainable, resilient, and productive under drought. Based on our current understanding of root-soil-microbiota interactions and available technologies, several approaches for microbiota-mediated drought tolerance could be considered for cereal plants (Fig. 2); the most common being manipulation of the soil microbiome through inoculation with SynComs and soil management practices, and manipulation of the host genome through modern breeding approaches.

5.1. Manipulating the soil microbiota

Inoculation of SynComs could be used to achieve a targeted manipulation of cereal microbiomes under drought stress, in which highly abundant microbial species with plant growth-promoting traits are assembled following novel compositional formulas that either build or mimic patterns observed in nature. The SynCom constructed from sugarcane-associated and maize-associated microbes resulted in increased biomass, improved drought tolerance, and enhanced root system development in maize under laboratory conditions (Armanhi et al., 2018, 2021). SynCom containing 53 Arabidopsis-associated bacteria and directly added to field sites also had a positive effect on sorghum growth in a four-week experiment (Qi et al., 2022). Although SynCom provides a promising platform for mitigating drought effects, several challenges, such as maintaining the long-term stability in the field, the complexity of dealing with indigenous microorganisms, their compatibility with different plant genotypes, the disruption by environmental conditions, and microbial evolution limit its wide-scale implementation (Li et al., 2024). For instance, many lineages of a SynCom designed through identification of host exudates and microbial networks were lost from the community, when inoculated seeds were grown either in vitro or a native field setting of sorghum (Fonseca-garcía et al., 2023). One strategy to overcome these challenges is to select microbes based on the native soil microbiome profiles to increase the potential for the inclusion of habitat-adapted strains with desired functions. The SynCom consisted of 21 bacterial strains, originating from three different native soils, which helped to confer drought resistance to maize plants (Jiang et al., 2023). Although the persistence of the SynCom was not monitored in the native soils, another study on wheat showed that it dropped dramatically after two weeks (Liu et al., 2022). These observations suggest that SynComs may be short-lived in soil, and their use may thereby be limited by the need for repeated applications. Unlike SynComs, other management practices that enrich the resident communities of microbes associated with crops through whole microbiota transplantations (Debray et al., 2022), host-mediated engineering of the microbiome (Jochum et al., 2019), and conditioning of the soil microbiota to use root-soil interactions and legacy effects (Buchenau et al., 2022; Carter et al., 2023) have long-lasting effects and can be used to engineer crops-associated microbial communities under drought. We speculate that these approaches are important for an understanding of microbial eco-evolutionary responses to drought stress as well as plant-microbe interactions in agricultural settings, but are not a pragmatic agronomic solution for cereal cultivation.

Agricultural practices including crop rotation (Renwick et al., 2021), conservation tillage (Madejon et al., 2023), intercropping (Pivato et al., 2021), and modification of soil physicochemical properties through the application of organic amendments (Hartman et al., 2018; Omatayo et al., 2021) can promote soil microbial diversity and thus can contribute to plant drought resilience. However, there are many challenges associated with this due to the complex interactions between host plants, agricultural practices, and soil properties. For example, the interaction between genotype and specific soil parameters such as soil type, soil pH, microbial biomass, soil sodium, and iron levels (Si et al., 2021), and soil depths (Naylor et al., 2023) determined the cluster of drought-enriched bacteria. Studies on microbial legacy effects also indicate that host-induced legacies can interact with drought-induced legacies in agricultural cropping systems. Lozano et al. (2022) showed that grassland species with a strong variation in root traits grown under drought history conditions cause variations in plant-soil-microbiome interactions and plant performance. The interaction between drought- and host-induced legacies was also reported by Kuerban et al. (2023), who found that species-specific conditioning of soils had significant effects on crop growth, but the effect differed greatly among crop species and depended on both conditioning crop identity and drought legacy. These observations suggest variations in the host genetic traits, soil properties, and the drought history of soil microbiota may cause variations in plant-soil-microbiome interactions and plant performance.

Interactions between organic farming, soil properties, and plant genotypes can also drive structural and functional adaptations of the root microbiome to drought stress (Breitkreuz et al., 2021) or may disrupt the dynamics of microbiota in cereals under drought stress (Babalola et al., 2022; Kelly et al., 2023). Kelly et al. (Kelly et al., 2023) showed that organic cultivation strategies (compost application and/or cover crops) that stimulate microbes in the wheat rhizosphere may be less successful under water limitation, especially when high inherent soil organic matter and biological activity can support the mineralization of residue nitrogen without added investment in root inputs. Mutually, plant cues such as root exudation that stimulate the microbial release of nutrients for plant regrowth after drought may not occur or may not play a role in nutrient-rich agricultural soils, where sufficient nutrients are available for plant growth (de Vries et al., 2020). These results indicate the smart applications of agricultural practices to increase microbial-based drought resilience in cereals. For that, a mechanistic understanding of the plant-soil-microbiota interactions in agricultural settings through computational methods such as machine learning and artificial intelligence will be essential for processing the enormous volumes of data required to identify interacting or synergistic effects between soil properties, soil manipulation practices (e.g. organic matter, SynCom, cropping systems), host genetics, host-induced legacy effects, and different environmental factors such as drought stress and its legacy on native soil microbiota from vast datasets.

5.2. Manipulation of the host genome

Manipulation of the host genotype is another promising approach for harnessing the cereal microbiota to increase drought resilience. For that, the first step is the selection of wild and semi-domesticated genotypes showing natural variation in traits related to plant-microbiome interactions. Considering the importance of soil-related parameters, a comprehensive microbiome survey in different locations with gradients of water availability and soil attributes at realistic field conditions is required to screen a large genetic diversity of cereals. By taking advantage of high-throughput (HTP) phenotyping platforms as well as advances in metabolomics, precise phenotypic and metabolomics data can be acquired and integrated with microbiome data to select genotypes based on root traits such as root exudates and morphology (Fig. 3). Automatic image analysis software such as X-ray tomography (CT), positron emission tomography (PET), magnetic resonance imaging (MRI), and electromagnetic inductance (EMI) that provide 3/4-D images

Fig. 3. A schematic overview of the proposed strategies to integrate microbiota manipulations into plant selection and breeding. (A) For microbiota-mediated improvement of the host genomes, the first step is the selection of wild/semi-domesticated genotypes showing natural variation in traits related to plant-microbiome interactions. Comprehensive microbiome surveys in different locations with gradients of water availability and soil traits at realistic field conditions are required to screen a large genetic diversity of cereals for microbiota-based approaches (Locations 1 and 2). (B) Integrating large-scale environmental metagenomics with metabolomics, HTP, and plant genomics (GWAS) is proposed to provide wider insights into plant-microbiota interactions. (C) By using these approaches, the differences between wild and domesticated plants are detected (shown in the dotted line box), and then the selected plants with positive traits to microbiota recruitment can be utilized for genome editing. (D) *De novo* domestication assists in introducing domestication genes into wild crop relatives. It could start from the selection of targeted genes, molecular design, plasmid construction, and rapid domestication by genome editing through CRISPR-Cas9 mutagenesis using *Agrobacterium*-mediated transformation. (E) The genetically manipulated plant driven from the wild genotype through *de novo* domestication is shown in the dotted line box with the color blue. These genotypes can provide diverse genomic resources for future functional genomic study and breeding to produce microbiome-based drought-resilient genotypes. One direct approach is conventional breeding in which two parents are crossed to obtain progenies. The transgenes are segregated in the progenies, and the selected plants have a high chance of fewer or no transgenes. (F) Novel technologies such as growth acceleration methods (e.g. speed breeding) and other technologies like HTP can accelerate the development of such novel plant genotypes. Rapid molecular phenotyping by using PCR can also identify Cas9-free plants. (G) Phenotypic evaluations such as yield and resilience to drought are performed in different field sites to create new genotypes.

of root systems show significant potential for studying root architectural traits without disturbing the root system under field conditions (Atkinson et al., 2019). Metabolomics is another emerging field, with some limitations in sampling techniques, the sensitivity of current metabolomics platforms, and the difficulties in differentiating between products from the microbe and plant fractions (Salem et al., 2022). For instance, in the case of sampling methods, hydroponic collection methods are limited by the artificial growth environment, affecting root morphology and physiology, whereas, samples taken from natural soils can show complexity due to chemicals originating from plant and microbial metabolites, which can confound identification of the origin of derived metabolites (Williams and de Vries, 2020). The collection of unaltered root exudates targeting the entire root system which can be more comparable with the field conditions may be an appropriate approach under drought stress (Williams and de Vries, 2020). The 'quick and dirty' hybrid technique where plants are grown in natural soils followed by a root washing step and hydroponic exudate sampling can provide evidence of genotypic differences under drought stress (Ghatak et al., 2022), and can thereby be used for the selection of cereal genotypes in field experiments.

The availability of genomics platforms has made it easier to identify genes involved in drought tolerance in cereals (Bhanbhro et al., 2024). Genome-wide association studies (GWAS) represent a potentially powerful, unbiased method to connect host-responsive microbes to the host genetic loci influencing their colonization (Deng et al., 2021). GWAS studies in rice and wheat, for example, have shown that plant genetics affects the recruitment of fungal communities and that certain fungi affect cereal yields under drought (Andreo-Jimenez et al., 2023; Lehnert et al., 2018). In drought-stressed rice, genes located around SNPs associating with fungi are involved in the plant immune system, abiotic stress responses, and cell wall remodeling processes (Andreo-Jimenez et al., 2023). Two regions on the wheat chromosomes 3D and 7D associated with the response to mycorrhizae under drought, embraced several well-known transcription factors such as AREB/ABF, AP2/ERF, bZIP, MYB, and MYC related to drought and osmotic stress, or interaction with symbionts (Lehnert et al., 2018). GWAS studies performed in sorghum (Deng et al., 2021; Watts-Williams et al., 2019), wheat (Lehnert et al., 2017), and millet (Y. Wang et al., 2022) have shown that factors controlling root microbiome associations are involved primarily in the biosynthesis of specialized metabolites, hormone signaling, nutrient uptake, the plant immune system, cell wall

integrity, and plasma membrane development. Apart from GWAS studies, integrating genome analysis with gene co-expression network analysis is another potentially effective approach to identifying candidate genes. Other studies pointed at genes coding for plant immune receptors (e.g., NLRs and RLKs), iron regulator FIT (bHLH), and the water channel aquaporin SITIP2.3 as the main candidates for rhizosphere microbiota assembly in wild and domesticated genotypes of barley and tomato (Escudero-martinez et al., 2022; Oyserman et al., 2022). These observations show that investigation of genomic differences among cereals assists in identifying genotypes with beneficial microbiota associations and related genes. Table 2 summarizes the GWAS studies carried out to date on cereal root microbiomes.

To harness the potential of crop wild ancestors for microbiota assembly and stress tolerance, plant breeding, and genetic engineering approaches can be used to introduce or modify genes related to root-microbiota interactions. For that, three different scenarios have been suggested:

i) by combining traits from the genetic backgrounds of wild species, breeding programs can create cereal cultivars with improved abilities to interact with beneficial microbiota. For instance, the production of synthetic hexaploid wheat, to broaden the genetic variation contributed by the D genome of *Aegilops tauschii* (Gholizadeh et al., 2022; Lehnert et al., 2018), could improve the microbial-mediated drought resilience of bread wheat; ii) transformation of microbiome-associated loci from wild ancestors to modern cereals. Since host traits involved in microbiome assembly are complex and multifactorial (e.g. plant immune system, metabolites, and root traits), these genetically regulated responses may not work in a predictable way (Raaijmakers and Kiers, 2022); iii) *de novo* domestication that aims to introduce relatively the few loci related to domestication with clear functional information into the wild cereal relatives to capitalize on the broad genetic diversity of the latter (Escudero-martinez and Bulgarelli, 2023; Raaijmakers and Kiers, 2022). In short, the route of *de novo* domestication strategy could start from the selection of wild or semi-domesticated plants with root-based traits of interest, followed by rapid domestication by CRISPR-Cas9 mutagenesis, conventional breeding, phenotypic screening, and field evaluation to create new genotypes that meet the biosafety assessments, as depicted in Fig. 3. Considering the fast-paced development of omics approaches, the way is paved for the successful implementation of breeding/engineering for the root-soil-microbiome interactions in the years to come.

Table 2

Summary list of genome-wide association studies to date connected host-responsive microbes to the host genetic loci in cereals.

Cereal Plant	Candidate gene/s	Gene functions	Microbe/s	Conditions	Reference
Rice (<i>Oryza sativa</i>)	DEFL, EXO70, RALFL, genes related to peroxidase and xylosyltransferase	Plant immunity, abiotic stress responses, and cell wall remodeling processes	Fungi	Drought	(Andreo-Jimenez et al. 2023)
Sorghum (<i>Sorghum bicolor</i>)	CAL2, XYL, RGA2	Remodeling of plant cell walls, Plant immune system	Bacteria	No-drought	(Deng et al. 2021)
Barley (<i>Hordeum vulgare</i>)	NLR, XTH, and an unknown function protein	Plant immunity, cell wall modifications	Bacteria	No-drought	(Escudero-martinez et al. 2022)
Wheat (<i>Triticum aestivum</i>)	LRR, CLC, SKU5, CSSP, CK1, MTAs	defense mechanisms, stress response, cell walls associated structures, genome-wide reprogramming	Fungi	No-drought	(Lehnert et al. 2017)
Wheat (<i>Triticum aestivum</i>)	AREB/ABF, AP2/ERF, bZIP, MYB, MYC, LEA, HSP, 6-SFT	Transcription factors and responsive genes associated with drought stress tolerance and response to mycorrhizae	Fungi	Drought	(Lehnert et al. 2018)
Maize (<i>Zea mays</i>)	Two genes with unknown proteins, AUXILIN- LIKE1, and AUXILIN- LIKE2	Root hair physiology and plant immune system	Bacteria	No-drought	(Meier et al. 2022)
Millet (<i>Setaria italica</i>)	RPM1, RGA2, HSL1, CRKs, LRR-RLKs, flavonoids and diterpenes biosynthesis, amyA, alpha-N-arabinofuranosidase, beta-glucuronosyltransferase, BRI1, DELLA protein, EFR3, PI-PLC, SDR, ARR1, Acid phosphatase, Mg ²⁺ transporter, H ⁺ -transporting ATPase, E3 ubiquitin protein ligase	immunity, metabolites, hormone signaling, and nutrient uptake	Bacteria	No-drought	(Y. Wang et al. 2022)

6. Conclusions and future perspectives

Plant roots share their habitat with thousands of soil microorganisms some of which may have positive effects on soil health and plant resilience to drought. It has been well documented that the tripartite interactions between host signatures, soil properties, and drought stress determine root microbiome composition. However, there are several extra dimensions of the complexity in the root-soil-microbiota associations due to interacting or synergistic effects between wide ranges of root-, soil-, agricultural practice-, and drought-related features (e.g. intensity, duration, frequency). Different host traits including root exudates, root architectural and morphological traits, and plant immune systems interact not only with each other but also with soil properties, agricultural practices, and drought exerting a significant effect on the root microbial diversity, activity, and function with consequences for soil carbon and nutrient cycling as well as plant resilience and fitness under water deficit. Perhaps one of the largest challenges is the need for improved knowledge of variation in root traits across a broad range of genotypes, soils, environmental conditions, and agricultural practices. To address these issues, developing efficient, cost-effective, simple, and reproducible methods to collect data, which can be applied under realistic field conditions, is a critical step. Increased throughput from the automated phenotyping platforms, genomics, metagenomics, and metabolomics as well as advances in computational methods such as analytical pipelines, machine learning, and artificial intelligence can open exciting avenues in applying smart agriculture for harnessing plant-soil-microbiota interactions. With such information, researchers can predict the consequences of the selection of genetic materials and cultivation changes of crops for increasing both soil nutrients and plant production in agricultural settings suffering from water limitations. Using comprehensive microbiome, GWAS, metabolomics, and root phenotyping studies performed in different locations and sites with gradients of water availability and soil attributes can help to identify varieties that show strong resilience to drought and related root traits/genes. Such genotypes or accessions can provide insights into the adaptive (epi)-genomics processes as well as their evolution with drought-adapted microbiota in soils, indicating the essential interactions that make wild species/local accessions more resilient to drought stress. By identifying sources of variation in root-based traits between cereals and their wild relatives, we can learn how this variation may offer opportunities for plant breeders to develop the next generation of cereals optimized for root-soil-microbiota associations. Latest innovations in genome-editing technology, such as CRISPR/Cas9 systems could be useful for plant breeders in modifying the cereal genome, as needed, to develop microbial-based drought-tolerant cultivars. The advantages of incorporating these novel plant breeding technologies with agricultural management will result in more sustainable agricultural settings. A new research field could then be considered to investigate the priority for host genome manipulations between the development of microbiota-mediated drought-resistant genotypes and the development of genotypes that are putatively adapted to microbiota-mediated drought-resilient cropping systems. We suggest that future modern breeding approaches should cooperate with agricultural practices to attain productivity in cereals by harnessing root-soil-microbiota interactions.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Somayeh Gholizadeh: Writing – original draft, Writing – review & editing. **Iman Nemati:** Writing – review & editing. **Mette Vestergård Madsen:** Writing – review & editing. **Christopher James Barnes:** Writing – review & editing. **Enoch Narh Kudjordjie:** Writing – review & editing. **Mogens Nicolaisen:** Writing – review & editing, Conceptualization.

Conflict of interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

Data Availability

No data was used for the research described in the article.

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Authors' contributions

The first author designed and wrote the manuscript under the supervision of Professor Mogens Nicolaisen. Other authors reviewed, commented, and approved the manuscript. The figures were designed by Iman Nemati and created with BioRender (BioRender.com).

References

- Abera, S., Shimels, M., Tessema, T., Raaijmakers, J.M., Dini-andreote, F., 2022. Back to the roots: defining the core microbiome of *Sorghum bicolor* in agricultural field soils from the centre of origin. *FEMS Microbiol. Ecol.* 98, 1–9. <https://doi.org/10.1093/femsec/fiac136>.
- Acharya, S.M., Yee, M.O., Diamond, S., Andeer, P.F., Baig, N.F., Aladesanmi, O.T., 2023. Fine scale sampling reveals early differentiation of rhizosphere microbiome from bulk soil in young *Brachypodium* plant roots. *ISME Commun.* 3 (1), 54. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s43705-023-00265-1>.
- Ali, S., Tyagi, A., Park, S., Mir, R.A., Mushtaq, M., Bhat, B., Mahmoudi, H., Bae, H., 2022. Deciphering the plant microbiome to improve drought tolerance: Mechanisms and perspectives. *Environ. Exp. Bot.* 201, 104933 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envexpbot.2022.104933>.
- Amadou, A., Song, A., Tang, Z.X., Li, Y., Wang, E.Z., Lu, Y.Q., Liu, X.D., Yi, K., Zhang, B., Fan, F., 2020. The effects of organic and mineral fertilization on soil enzyme activities and bacterial community in the below- And above-ground parts of wheat. *Agronomy* 10, 1452. <https://doi.org/10.3390/agronomy10101452>.
- Anderson, A.J., Hortin, J.M., Jacobson, A.R., Britt, D.W., McLean, J.E., 2023. Changes in Metal-Chelating Metabolites Induced by Drought and a Root Microbiome in Wheat. *Plants* 12, 1209. <https://doi.org/10.3390/plants12061209>.
- Andreo-jimenez, B., Vandenkoornhuysse, P., Van, A.L., Heutinck, A., Duhamel, M., Kadam, N., Jagadish, K., Ruyter-spira, C., Bouwmeester, H., 2019. Plant host and drought shape the root associated fungal microbiota in rice. *PeerJ* 7, e7463 <https://doi.org/10.7717/peerj.7463>.
- Andreo-Jimenez, B., Beest, D.E., Kruijer, W., Vannier, N., Kadam, N.N., Melandri, G., Jagadish, S.V.K., Linden, G.Van Der, Ruyter-Spira, C., Vandenkoornhuysse, P., Bouwmeester, H.J., 2023. Genetic Mapping of the Root Mycobiota in Rice and its Role in Drought Tolerance. *Rice* 16, 26. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12284-023-00641-4>.
- Aparna, S., Nunna, D., 2022. Rhizosphere functioning and rhizo-microbiome of two contrasting genotypes of rice under drought- induced conditions. *Res. Sq.* 1–26 <https://doi.org/10.21203/rs.3.rs-2267712/v1>.
- Araújo, V.L.V.P., Fracetto, G.G.M., Silva, A.M.M., Pereira, A.P. de A., Freitas, C.C.G., Barros, F.M. do R., Santana, M.C., Feiler, H.P., Matteoli, F.P., Fracetto, F.J.C., Cardoso, E.J.B.N., 2023. Potential of growth-promoting bacteria in maize (*Zea mays* L.) varies according to soil moisture. *Microbiol. Res.* 271, 127352 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.micres.2023.127352>.
- Armanhi, J.S.L., Souza, R.S.C., de, Damasceno, N., de, B., Araújo, L.M. de, Imperial, J., Arruda, P., 2018. A community-based culture collection for targeting novel plant growth-promoting bacteria from the sugarcane microbiome. *Front. Plant Sci.* 8, 2191. (<https://doi.org/10.3389/fpls.2017.02191>).
- Armanhi, J.S.L., Souza, R.S.C., de, Biazotti, B.B., Yassitepe, J.E., de, C.T., Arruda, P., 2021. Modulating Drought Stress Response of Maize by a Synthetic Bacterial Community. *Front. Microbiol.* 12, 747541 <https://doi.org/10.3389/fmicb.2021.747541>.
- Atkinson, J.A., Pound, M.P., Bennett, M.J., Wells, D.M., 2019. Uncovering the hidden half of plants using new advances in root phenotyping. *Curr. Opin. Biotechnol.* 55, 1–8. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.copbio.2018.06.002>.
- Ayangbenro, A.S., Chukwuneme, C.F., Ayilara, M.S., Kutu, F.R., Khantsi, M., Adeleke, B. S., Babalola, O.O., Glick, B.R., 2022. Harnessing the Rhizosphere Soil Microbiome of Organically Amended Soil for Plant Productivity. *Agronomy* 12, 3179. <https://doi.org/10.3390/agronomy12123179>.
- Azarbad, H., Constant, P., Giard-Laliberté, C., Bainard, L.D., Yergeau, E., 2018. Water stress history and wheat genotype modulate rhizosphere microbial response to drought. *Soil Biol. Biochem.* 126, 228–236. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.soilbio.2018.08.017>.

- Azarbad, H., Tremblay, J., Giard-Laliberté, C., Bainard, L.D., Yergeau, E., 2020. Four decades of soil water stress history together with host genotype constrain the response of the wheat microbiome to soil moisture. *FEMS Microbiol. Ecol.* 96 (7) <https://doi.org/10.1093/FEMSEC/FIAA098>.
- Azarbad, H., Bainard, L.D., Agoussar, A., Tremblay, J., Yergeau, E., 2022. The response of wheat and its microbiome to contemporary and historical water stress in a field experiment. *ISME Commun.* 2, 62. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s43705-022-00151-2>.
- Babalola, B.J., Li, J., Willing, C.E., Zheng, Y., Wang, Y.L., Gan, H.Y., Li, X.C., Wang, C., Adams, C.A., Gao, C., Guo, L.D., 2022. Nitrogen fertilisation disrupts the temporal dynamics of arbuscular mycorrhizal fungal hyphae but not spore density and community composition in a wheat field. *N. Phytol.* 234 (6), 2057–2072. <https://doi.org/10.1111/nph.18043>.
- Bahraminia, M., Zarei, M., Ronaghi, A., Sepehri, M., Etesami, H., 2020. Ionic and biochemical responses of maize plant (*Zea mays* L.) inoculated with *Funneliformis mosseae* to water-deficit stress. *Rhizosphere* 16, 100269. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rhisph.2020.100269>.
- Balasubramanian, V.K., Dampanaboina, L., Cobos, C.J., Yuan, N., Xin, Z., Mendu, V., 2021. Induced secretion system mutation alters rhizosphere bacterial composition in *Sorghum bicolor* (L.) Moench. *Planta* 253, 33. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00425-021-03569-5>.
- Banerjee, S., Walder, F., Büchi, L., Meyer, M., Held, A.Y., Gatteringer, A., Keller, T., Charles, R., Heijden, M.G.A. Van Der, 2019. Agricultural intensification reduces microbial network complexity and the abundance of keystone taxa in roots. *ISME J.* 13, 1722–1736. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41396-019-0383-2>.
- Barnawal, D., Bharti, N., Pandey, S.S., Pandey, A., Chantotiya, C.S., Kalra, A., 2017. Plant growth-promoting rhizobacteria enhance wheat salt and drought stress tolerance by altering endogenous phytohormone levels and TaCTR1/TaDREB2 expression. *Physiol. Plant.* 161, 502–5017. <https://doi.org/10.1111/ppl.12614>.
- Basirat, M., Mousavi, S.M., Abbaszadeh, S., Ebrahimi, M., Zarebanadkouki, M., 2019. The rhizosphere: a potential root trait helping plants to tolerate drought stress. *Plant Soil* 445, 565–575. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11104-019-04334-0>.
- Berens, M.L., Wolinska, K.W., Spaepen, S., Ziegler, J., Nobori, T., Nair, A., Krüller, V., Winkelmüller, T.M., Wang, Y., Mine, A., Becker, D., Garrido-Oter, R., Schulze-Lefert, P., Tsuda, K., 2019. Balancing trade-offs between biotic and abiotic stress responses through leaf age-dependent variation in stress hormone cross-talk. *PNAS* 116 (6), 2364–2373. <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.1817233116>.
- Bernardo, L., Morcia, C., Carletti, P., Ghizzoni, R., Badeck, F.W., Rizza, F., Lucini, L., Terzi, V., 2017. Proteomic insight into the mitigation of wheat root drought stress by arbuscular mycorrhizae. *J. Proteom.* 169, 21–32. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jprot.2017.03.024>.
- Bernardo, L., Carletti, P., Badeck, F.W., Rizza, F., Morcia, C., Ghizzoni, R., Roupheal, Y., Colla, G., Terzi, V., Lucini, L., 2019. Metabolomic responses triggered by arbuscular mycorrhiza enhance tolerance to water stress in wheat cultivars. *Plant Physiol. Biochem.* 137, 203–212. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.plaphy.2019.02.007>.
- Bhanbho, N., Wang, H., Yang, H., Xu, X., Jakhar, A.M., Shalmani, A., Zhang, R.-X., Baksh, Q., Akbar, G., Jakhro, M.I., Khan, Y., Chen, K.-M., 2024. Plant Stress Revisiting the molecular mechanisms and adaptive strategies associated with drought stress tolerance in common wheat (*Triticum aestivum* L.). *Plant Stress* 11, 100298. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.stress.2023.100298>.
- Bilyera, N., Zhang, X., Duddek, P., Fan, L., Banfield, C.C., Schlüter, S., Carminati, A., Kaestner, A., Ahmed, M.A., Kuzakov, Y., Dippold, M.A., Spielvogel, S., Razavi, B.S., 2021. Maize genotype-specific exudation strategies: an adaptive mechanism to increase microbial activity in the rhizosphere. *Soil Biol. Biochem.* 162, 108426. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.soilbio.2021.108426>.
- Bogati, K., Walczak, M., 2022. The Impact of Drought Stress on Soil Microbial Community, Enzyme Activities and Plants. *Agronomy* 12, 189. <https://doi.org/10.3390/agronomy12010189>.
- Breitkreuz, C., Herzog, L., Buscot, F., Reitz, T., Tarkka, M., 2021. Interactions between soil properties, agricultural management and cultivar type drive structural and functional adaptations of the wheat rhizosphere microbiome to drought. *Environ. Microbiol.* 23 (10), 5866–5882. <https://doi.org/10.1111/1462-2920.15607>.
- Bremer, E., Krämer, R., 2019. Responses of Microorganisms to Osmotic Stress. *Annu. Rev. Microbiol.* 73, 313–334. <https://doi.org/10.1146/annurev-micro-020518-115504>.
- Buchenau, N., Kleunen, M. van, Wilschut, R.A., 2022. Direct and legacy-mediated drought effects on plant performance are species-specific and depend on soil community composition. *Oikos*, e08959. <https://doi.org/10.1111/oik.08959>.
- Caddell, D.F., Louie, K., Bowen, B., Sievert, J.A., Hollingsworth, J., Dahlberg, J., Purdom, E., Northen, T., Coleman-Derr, D., 2023. Drought shifts sorghum root metabolite and microbiome profiles and enriches for piperolic acid. *Phybiomes* 7 (4), 449–463. <https://doi.org/10.1094/PBIOMES-02-23-0011-R>.
- Canarini, A., Schmidt, H., Fuchslueger, L., Martin, V., Herbold, C.W., Zezula, D., Gündler, P., Hasibeder, R., Jecmenica, M., Bahn, M., Richter, A., 2021. Ecological memory of recurrent drought modifies soil processes via changes in soil microbial community. *Nat. Commun.* 12, 5308. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41467-021-25675-4>.
- Carlson, R., Tugizimana, F., Steenkamp, P.A., Dubery, I.A., Idris, A., Labuschagne, N., 2020. Rhizobacteria-induced systemic tolerance against drought stress in *Sorghum bicolor* (L.) Moench. *Microbiol. Res.* 232, 126388. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.micres.2019.126388>.
- Carter, K.R., Nachtsheim, A.C., Dickman, L.T., Moore, E.R., Negi, S., Heneghan, J.P., Sabella, A.J., Steadman, C.R., Albright, M.B.N., Anderson, C.M., Louise, C., Rose, H. C., Jeffrey, J.H., Nicholas, M.H., Marina, O.C., Musa, D., Newman, B.D., Perkins, G. B., Twary, S., Sevanto, S., 2023. Drought conditioning of rhizosphere microbiome influences maize water use traits. *Plant Soil* 11 (2), e01476–22. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11104-023-06204-2>.
- Carvalho, L.C., Rincon-florez, V.A., Brewer, P.B., Beveridge, C.A., Dennis, P.G., Schenk, P.M., 2019. The ability of plants to produce strigolactones affects rhizosphere community composition of fungi but not bacteria. *Rhizosphere* 9, 18–26. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rhisph.2018.10.002>.
- Chai, Y.N., Schachtman, D.P., 2022. Root exudates impact plant performance under abiotic stress. *Trends Plant Sci.* 27 (1), 80–91. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tplants.2021.08.003>.
- Chandrasekaran, M., 2022. Arbuscular Mycorrhizal Fungi Mediated Enhanced Biomass, Root Morphological Traits and Nutrient Uptake under Drought Stress: A Meta-Analysis. *J. Fungi* 8, 660. <https://doi.org/10.3390/jof8070660>.
- Chen, L., Xin, X.L., Zhang, J.B., Redmile-Gordon, M., Nie, G.S., Wang, Q.Y., 2019. Soil Characteristics Overwhelm Cultivar Effects on the Structure and Assembly of Root-Associated Microbiomes of Modern Maize. *Pedosphere* 29 (3), 360–373. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S1002-0160\(17\)60370-9](https://doi.org/10.1016/S1002-0160(17)60370-9).
- Cheng, S., Zou, Y.N., Kuća, K., Hashem, A., Abd-Allah, E.F., Wu, Q.S., 2021. Elucidating the mechanisms underlying enhanced drought tolerance in plants mediated by arbuscular mycorrhizal fungi. *Front. Microbiol.* 12, 809473. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fmicb.2021.809473>.
- Christel, A., Maron, P., Ranjard, L., 2021. Impact of farming systems on soil ecological quality: a meta-analysis. *Environ. Chem. Lett.* 19, 4603–4625. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10311-021-01302-y>.
- Curá, J.A., Franz, D.R., Filosofia, J.E., Balestrasse, K.B., Burgueño, L.E., 2017. Inoculation with *Azospirillum* sp. and *Herbaspirillum* sp. Bacteria Increases the Tolerance of Maize to Drought Stress. *Microorganisms* 5, 41. <https://doi.org/10.3390/microorganisms5030041>.
- Debray, R., Socolar, Y., Kaulbach, G., Guzman, A., Hernandez, C.A., Curley, R., Dhond, A., Bowles, T., Koskella, B., 2022. Water stress and disruption of mycorrhizas induce parallel shifts in phyllosphere microbiome composition. *N. Phytol.* 234 (6), 2018–2031. <https://doi.org/10.1111/nph.17817>.
- Deng, S., Caddell, D.F., Xu, G., Dahlen, L., Washington, L., Yang, J., Coleman-Derr, D., 2021. Genome wide association study reveals plant loci controlling heritability of the rhizosphere microbiome. *ISME J.* 15, 3181–3194. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41396-021-00993-z>.
- Ding, X., Peng, X., Chen, Z., Li, Y., Mao, L., Xie, H., Cai, Y., 2020. Microbiota community assembly in wild rice (*Oryza longistaminata*) in response to drought stress shows phylogenetic conservation, stochasticity, and aboveground-belowground patterns. *Res. Sq.* 1–27. <https://doi.org/10.21203/rs.3.rs-40339/v1>.
- Dong, M., Kuramae, E.E., Zhao, M., Li, R., Shen, Q., Kowalchuk, G.A., 2023. Tomato growth stage modulates bacterial communities across different soil aggregate sizes and disease levels. *ISME Commun.* 3, 104. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s43705-023-00312-x>.
- Durr, J., Reyt, G., Spaepen, S., Hilton, S., Meehan, C., Qi, W., Kamiya, T., Flis, P., Dickinson, H.G., Feher, A., Shivshankar, U., Pavagadhi, S., Swarup, S., Salt, D., Bending, G.D., Gutierrez-marcos, J., 2021. A Novel Signaling Pathway Required for Arabidopsis Endodermal Root Organization Shapes the Rhizosphere Microbiome. *Plant Cell Physiol.* 62 (2), 248–261. <https://doi.org/10.1093/pcp/pcaa170>.
- Durrer, A., Gumiere, T., Rumenos, M., Zagatto, G., Feiler, H.P., Marcos, A., Silva, M., Longaresi, H., Homma, S.K., Cardoso, E.J.B.N., 2021. Organic farming practices change the soil bacteria community, improving soil quality and maize crop yields. *PeerJ* 1–24. <https://doi.org/10.7717/peerj.11985>.
- El-daim, I.A.A., Bejai, S., Meijer, J., 2019. *Bacillus velezensis* 5113 Induced Metabolic and Molecular Reprogramming during Abiotic Stress Tolerance in Wheat. *Sci. Rep.* 9, 16282. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-019-52567-x>.
- Escudero-martinez, C., Bulgarelli, D., 2023. Engineering the Crop Microbiota Through Host Genetics. *Annu. Rev.* 61, 257–277. <https://doi.org/10.1146/annurev-phyto-021621-121447>.
- Escudero-martinez, C., Coulter, M., Terrazas, R.A., Foito, A., Kapadia, R., Pietrangelo, L., Maver, M., Sharma, R., Aprile, A., Morris, J., Hedley, P.E., Maurer, A., Pellen, K., Naclerio, G., Mimmo, T., Barton, G.J., Waugh, R., Abbott, J., Bulgarelli, D., 2022. Identifying plant genes shaping microbiota composition in the barley rhizosphere. *Nat. Commun.* 13, 3443. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41467-022-31022-y>.
- Espinoza, C., Liang, Y., Stacey, G., 2017. Chitin receptor CERK1 links salt stress and chitin-triggered innate immunity in Arabidopsis. *Plant J.* 89, 984–995. <https://doi.org/10.1111/tpj.13437>.
- Favela, A., O. Bohn, M., D. Kent, A., 2021. Maize germplasm chronosequence shows crop breeding history impacts recruitment of the rhizosphere microbiome. *ISME J.* 15 (8) <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41396-021-00923-z>.
- Finkel, O.M., Salas-Gonzalez, I., Castrillo, G., Spaepen, S., Law, T.F., Teixeira, P.J.P.L., Corbin, Jones, D., Dangel, J.L., 2019. The effects of soil phosphorus content on plant microbiota are driven by the plant phosphate starvation response. *PLoS Biol.* 17 (11), e3000534. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pbio.3000534>.
- Fitzpatrick, C.R., Copeland, J., Wang, P.W., Guttman, D.S., Kotanen, P.M., Johnson, M.T. J., 2018. Assembly and ecological function of the root microbiome across angiosperm plant species. *PNAS* 115, E1157–E1165. <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.1717617115>.
- Fonseca-garcía, C., Wilson, A., Elmore, J., Pettinga, D., Atim, J., Pedraza, J., Huttmacher, R., Egbert, R., Coleman-derr, D. (2023). Defined synthetic microbial communities colonize and benefit field-grown sorghum. *BioRxiv.* <https://doi.org/10.1101/2023.05.30.542977>.
- Gaete, A., Pulgar, R., Hodar, C., Maldonado, J., Pavez, L., Zamorano, D., Pastenes, C., González, M., Franck, N., Mandakovic, D., 2021. Tomato Cultivars With Variable Tolerances to Water Deficit Differentially Modulate the Composition and Interaction Patterns of Their Rhizosphere Microbial Communities. *Front. Plant Sci.* 12, 688533. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpls.2021.688533>.
- Galindo-castañeda, T., Lynch, J.P., Six, J., Hartmann, M., 2022. Improving soil resource uptake by plants through capitalizing on synergies between root architecture and

- anatomy and root-associated microorganisms. *Front. Plant Sci.* 13, 827369 <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpls.2022.827369>.
- Galindo-Castañeda, T., Brown, K.M., Kuldau, G.A., Roth, G.W., Wenner, N.G., Ray, S., Schneider, H., Lynch, J.P., 2019. Root cortical anatomy is associated with differential pathogenic and symbiotic fungal colonization in maize. *Plant Cell Environ.* 42, 2999–3014. <https://doi.org/10.1111/pce.13615>.
- Galloway, A.F., Akhtar, J., Marcus, S.E., Fletcher, N., Field, K., Knox, P., 2020. Cereal root exudates contain highly structurally complex polysaccharides with soil-binding properties. *Plant J.* 103, 1666–1678. <https://doi.org/10.1111/tpj.14852>.
- Gao, C., Montoya, L., Xu, L., Madera, M., Hollingsworth, J., Purdom, E., Singan, V., Vogel, J., Huttmacher, R.B., Dahlberg, J.A., Coleman-derr, D., Lemaux, P.G., Taylor, J.W., 2020. Fungal community assembly in drought-stressed sorghum shows stochasticity, selection, and universal ecological dynamics. *Nat. Commun.* 11, 34. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41467-019-13913-9>.
- Gao, C., Xu, L., Montoya, L., Madera, M., Hollingsworth, J., Chen, L., Purdom, E., Singan, V., Vogel, J., Huttmacher, R.B., Dahlberg, J.A., Coleman-Derr, D., Lemaux, P.G., Taylor, J.W., 2022. Co-occurrence networks reveal more complexity than community composition in resistance and resilience of microbial communities. *Nat. Commun.* 13, 3867. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41467-022-31343-y>.
- Gargallo-garriga, A., Preece, C., Sardans, J., Oravec, M., Urban, O., Peñuelas, J., 2018. Root exudate metabolomes change under drought and show limited capacity for recovery. *Sci. Rep.* 8, 12696. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-018-30150-0>.
- Gebauer, L., Bouffaud, M., Ganther, M., Yim, B., Vetterlein, D., Smalla, K., Buscot, F., Heintz-buschart, A., Tarkka, M.T., 2021. Soil Texture, Sampling Depth and Root Hairs Shape the Structure of ACC Deaminase Bacterial Community Composition in Maize Rhizosphere. *Front. Microbiol.* 12, 616828. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fmicb.2021.616828>.
- Gebauer, L., Breitzkreuz, C., Heintz-buschart, A., Reitz, T., Buscot, F., Tarkka, M., Bouffaud, M.-L., 2022. Water Deficit History Selects Plant Beneficial Soil Bacteria Differently Under Conventional and Organic Farming. *Front. Microbiol.* 13, 824437. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fmicb.2022.824437>.
- Ghaffari, M.R., Mirzaei, M., Ghabooli, M., Khatibi, B., Wu, Y., Zabet-moghaddam, M., Hajirezaei, M.R., Salekdeh, G.H., Sepehri, M., Mohammadi-nejad, G., Haynes, P.A., 2019. Root endophytic fungus *Piriformospora indica* improves drought stress adaptation in barley by metabolic and proteomic reprogramming. *Environ. Exp. Bot.* 157, 197–210. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envexpbot.2018.10.002>.
- Ghatak, A., Schindler, F., Bachmann, G., Engelmeier, D., Bajaj, P., Brenner, M., Fragner, L., Varshney, R.K., Subbarao, G.V., Chaturvedi, P., Weckwerth, W., 2022. Root exudation of contrasting drought-stressed pearl millet genotypes conveys varying biological nitrification inhibition (BNI) activity. *Biol. Fert. Soils* 58, 291–306. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00374-021-01578-w>.
- Gholizadeh, S., Mohammadi, S.-A., Salekdeh, G.H., 2022. Changes in root microbiome during wheat evolution. *BMC Microbiol.* 22, 64. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12866-022-02467-4>.
- Govindasamy, V., George, P., Kumar, M., Aher, L., Raina, S.K., Rane, J., Annapurna, K., Minhas, P.S., 2020. Multi-trait PGP rhizobacterial endophytes alleviate drought stress in a senescent genotype of sorghum [Sorghum bicolor (L.) Moench]. *3 Biotech* 10, 13. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s13205-019-2001-4>.
- Grover, M., Bodhankar, S., Sharma, A., Sharma, P., Singh, J., 2021. PGPR Mediated Alterations in Root Traits: Way Toward Sustainable Crop Production. *Front. Sustain. Food Syst.* 4, 618230. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fsufs.2020.618230>.
- Guevara-herandez, E., Arellano-Wattenbarger, G.L., Coronado, Y., Torre, M., de la Rocha, J., Aguirre-von-Wobeser, E., 2024. Drought induces substitution of bacteria within taxonomic groups in the rhizosphere of native maize from arid and tropical regions. *Rhizosphere* 29, 100835. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rhisph.2023.100835>.
- Hallett, P.D., Marin, M., Bending, G.D., George, T.S., Collins, C.D., Otten, W., 2022. Building soil sustainability from root-soil interface traits. *Trends Plant Sci.* 27 (7), 688–698. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tplants.2022.01.010>.
- Han, C., Zhou, W., Gu, Y., Wang, J., Zhou, Y., Xue, Y., Shi, Z., Siddique, K.H.M., 2024. Effects of tillage regime on soil aggregate-associated carbon, enzyme activity, and microbial community structure in a semiarid agroecosystem. *Front. Sustain. Food Syst.* <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11104-023-06453-1>.
- Hartman, K., van der Heijden, M.G.A., Witter, R.A., Banerjee, S., Walsler, J.C., Schlaeppi, K., 2018. Cropping practices manipulate abundance patterns of root and soil microbiome members paving the way to smart farming. *Microbiome* 6, 14. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s40168-017-0389-9>.
- He, D., Singh, S.K., Peng, L., Kaushal, R., Vilchez, J.I., Shao, C., Wu, X., Zheng, S., 2022. Flavonoid-attracted *Aeromonas* sp. from the Arabidopsis root microbiome enhances plant dehydration resistance. *ISME J.* 16, 2622–2632. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41396-022-01288-7>.
- Hestrin, R., Kan, M., Laffler, M., Wollard, J., Kimbrel, J.A., Ray, P., Blazewicz, S.J., Stuart, R., Craven, K., Firestone, M., Nuccio, E.E., Pett-Ridge, J., 2022. Plant-associated fungi support bacterial resilience following water limitation. *ISME J.* 16, 2752–2762. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41396-022-01308-6>.
- Holz, M., Zarebanadkouki, M., Kuzuyakov, Y., Pausch, J., Carminati, A., 2018. Root hairs increase rhizosphere extension and carbon input to soil. *Ann. Bot.* 121, 61–69. <https://doi.org/10.1093/aob/mcx127>.
- Horton, M.W., Bodenhausen, N., Beilsmith, K., Meng, D., Muegge, B.D., Nordborg, M., Subramanian, S., Vetter, M.M., Vilhja, B.J., Gordon, J.I., Bergelson, J., 2014. Genome-wide association study of Arabidopsis thaliana leaf microbial community. *Nat. Commun.* 5, 5320. <https://doi.org/10.1038/ncomms6320>.
- Hsu, P.-K., Dubeaux, G., Takahashi, Y., Schroeder, J.I., 2021. Signaling mechanisms in abscisic acid-mediated stomatal closure. *Plant J.* 105, 307–321. <https://doi.org/10.1111/tpj.15067>.
- Hu, Y., Xie, W., Chen, B., 2020. Arbuscular mycorrhiza improved drought tolerance of maize seedlings by altering photosystem II efficiency and the levels of key metabolites. *Chem. Biol. Technol. Agric.* 7, 20. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s40538-020-00186-4>.
- Huot, B., Castroverde, C.D.M., Velásquez, A.C., Hubbard, E., Pulman, J.A., Yao, J., Childs, K.L., Tsuda, K., Montgomery, B.L., He, S.Y., 2017. Dual impact of elevated temperature on plant defence and bacterial virulence in Arabidopsis. *Nat. Commun.* 8, 1–11. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41467-017-01674-2>.
- Imran, S., Ganugi, P., Arfaioli, P., Masoni, A., Pietramellara, G., 2023. Resilience of root and soil bacteria to drought stress depends on host plants colonization affinity towards arbuscular mycorrhiza fungi. *Eur. J. Soil Biol.* 118, 103540. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ejsobi.2023.103540>.
- Janda, M., Lamparova, L., Zubikova, A., Burketova, L., Martinec, J., Krcova, Z., 2019. Temporary heat stress suppresses PAMP-triggered immunity and resistance to bacteria in Arabidopsis thaliana. *Mol. Plant Pathol.* 20 (7), 1005–1012. <https://doi.org/10.1111/mpp.12799>.
- Jang, S., Youn, M., Hong, W., Kim, Y., Lee, E., Jung, K., 2020. Re-Analysis of 16S Amplicon Sequencing Data Reveals Soil Microbial Population Shifts in Rice Fields under Drought Condition. *Rice* 13, 44. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12284-020-00403-6>.
- Jerbi, M., Labidi, S., Laruelle, F., Tisserant, B., Jeddi, F., Ben, Sahraoui, A.L.-H., 2022. Mycorrhizal biofertilization improves grain yield and quality of hullless Barley (*Hordeum vulgare* ssp. nudum L.) under water stress conditions. *J. Cereal Sci.* 104, 103436. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jcs.2022.103436>.
- Ji, C., Liang, Z., Cao, H., Chen, Z., Kong, X., Xin, Z., He, M., Wang, J., Wei, Z., Xing, J., Li, C., Zhang, Y., Zhang, H., Sun, F., Li, J., Li, K., 2023. Transcriptome-based analysis of the effects of compound microbial agents on gene expression in wheat roots and leaves under salt stress. *Front. Plant Sci.* 14, 1109077. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpls.2023.1109077>.
- Jiang, M., Delgado-Baquerizo, M., Yuan, M.M., Ding, J., Yergeau, E., Zhou, J., Crowther, T.W., Liang, Y., 2023. Home-based microbial solution to boost crop growth in low-fertility soil. *N. Phytol.* 239, 752–765. <https://doi.org/10.1111/nph.18943>.
- Jochum, M.D., McWilliams, K.L., Pierson, E.A., Jo, Y.K., 2019. Host-mediated microbiome engineering (HMM) of drought tolerance in the wheat rhizosphere. *PLoS One* 14 (12), e0225933. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0225933>.
- Kakar, K.U., Ren, X., Nawaz, Z., Cui, Z., Li, B., Xie, G., Hassan, M.A., Ali, E., Sun, G., 2016. A consortium of rhizobacterial strains and biochemical growth elicitors improve cold and drought stress tolerance in rice (*Oryza sativa* L.). *Plant Biol.* 18, 471–483. <https://doi.org/10.1111/plb.12427>.
- Kamali, S., Mehraban, A., 2020. Nitroxin and arbuscular mycorrhizal fungi alleviate negative effects of drought stress on Sorghum bicolor yield through improving physiological and biochemical characteristics. *Plant Sign. Behav.* 15 (11), e1813998. <https://doi.org/10.1080/15592324.2020.1813998>.
- Kavamura, V.N., Hayat, R., Clark, I.M., Rossmann, M., Mendes, R., Hirsch, P.R., Mauchline, T.H., 2018. Inorganic nitrogen application affects both taxonomical and predicted functional structure of wheat rhizosphere bacterial communities. *Front. Microbiol.* 9, 1074. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fmicb.2018.01074>.
- Kavamura, V.N., Robinson, R.J., Hughes, D., Clark, I., Rossmann, M., Melo, I.S. de, Hirsch, P.R., Mendes, R., Mauchline, T.H., 2020. Wheat dwarfing influences selection of the rhizosphere microbiome. *Sci. Rep.* 10, 1452. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-020-58402-y>.
- Kelly, C., Byrne, P.F., Schipanski, M.E., Schneekloth, J., Calderón, F., Fonte, S.J., 2023. Soil management legacy interacts with wheat genotype to determine access to organic N in a dryland system. *Agric. Ecosyst. Environ.* 345, 108336. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.agee.2022.108336>.
- Kim, B., Westerhuis, J.A., Smilde, A.K., Floková, K., Suleiman, A.K.A., Kuramae, E.E., Bouwmeester, H.J., Zancarani, A., 2022. Effect of strigolactones on recruitment of the rice root-associated microbiome. *FEMS Microbiol. Ecol.* 98, 1–12. <https://doi.org/10.1093/femsec/fiac010>.
- Kim, N., Zabaloy, M.C., Guan, K., Villamil, M.B., 2020. Do cover crops benefit soil microbiome? A meta-analysis of current research. *Soil Biol. Biochem.* 142, 107701. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.soilbio.2019.107701>.
- Kristy, B., Carrell, A.A., Johnston, E., Cumming, J.R., Klingeman, D.M., Gwinn, K., Syring, K.C., Skalla, C., Emrich, S., Cregger, M.A., 2022. Chronic drought differentially alters the belowground microbiome of drought-tolerant and drought-susceptible genotypes of populus trichocarpa. *Phytobiomes J.* 6, 317–330. <https://doi.org/10.1094/BIOMES-12-21-0076-R>.
- Kuerban, M., Cong, W., Jing, J., Bezemer, T.M., 2023. Microbial soil legacies of crops under different water and nitrogen levels determine succeeding crop performance. *Plant Soil* 485, 167–180. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11104-022-05412-6>.
- Lebeis, S.L., Paredes, S.H., Lundberg, D.S., Breakfield, N., Gehring, J., McDonald, M., Glavina, T., Jones, C.D., 2015. Salicylic acid modulates colonization of the root microbiome by specific bacterial taxa. *Science* 349 (6250), 860–864. <https://doi.org/10.5061/dryad.238b2>.
- Lehnert, H., Serfling, A., Enders, M., Friedt, W., Ordon, F., 2017. Genetics of mycorrhizal symbiosis in winter wheat (*Triticum aestivum*). *N. Phytol.* 215, 779–791. <https://doi.org/10.1111/nph.14595>.
- Lehnert, H., Serfling, A., Friedt, W., Ordon, F., 2018. Genome-wide association studies reveal genomic regions associated with the response of wheat (*Triticum aestivum* L.) to mycorrhizae under drought stress conditions. *Front. Plant Sci.* 9, 1728. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpls.2018.01728>.
- Lephatsi, M., Nephali, L., Meyer, V., Piater, L.A., Buthelezi, N., Dubery, I.A., Opperman, H., Brand, M., Huysen, J., Tugizimana, F., 2022. Molecular mechanisms associated with microbial biostimulant-mediated growth enhancement, priming and drought stress tolerance in maize plants. *Sci. Rep.* 12, 10450. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-022-14570-7>.

- Li, G., Wang, K., Qin, Q., Li, Q., Mo, F., Nangia, V., Liu, Y., 2023. Integrated microbiome and metabolomic analysis reveal responses of rhizosphere bacterial communities and root exudate composition to drought and genotype in Rice (*Oryza sativa* L.). *Rice* 16, 19. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12284-023-00636-1>.
- Li, H., Guo, Q., Jing, Y., Liu, Z., Zheng, Z., Sun, Y., Xue, Q., Lai, H., 2020. Application of *Streptomyces pactum* Act12 Enhances Drought Resistance in Wheat. *J. Plant Growth Regul.* 39, 122–132. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00344-019-09968-z>.
- Li, M., Zhu, Y., Li, S., Zhang, W., Yin, C., Lin, Y., 2022. Regulation of Phytohormones on the Growth and Development of Plant Root Hair. *Front. Plant Sci.* 13, 865302 <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpls.2022.865302>.
- Li, S., Liu, S., Zhang, Q., Cui, M., Zhao, M., Li, N., Wang, S., Wu, R., Zhang, L., Cao, Y., Wang, L., 2022. The interaction of ABA and ROS in plant growth and stress resistances. *Front. Plant Sci.* 13, 1050132 <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpls.2022.1050132>.
- Li, X., Zheng, X., Yadav, N., Saha, S., Salama, E., Li, X., Wang, L., Jeon, B., 2024. Rational management of the plant microbiome for the Second Green Revolution. *Plant Commun.* 5, 100812 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.xplc.2024.100812>.
- Liu, H., Qiu, Z., Ye, J., Verma, J.P., Li, J., Singh, B.K., 2022. Effective colonisation by a bacterial synthetic community promotes plant growth and alters soil microbial community. *J. Sustain. Agric. Environ.* 1, 30–42. <https://doi.org/10.1002/sae2.12008>.
- Liu, T.-Y., Ye, N., Song, T., Cao, Y., Gao, B., Zhang, D., Zhu, F., Chen, M., Zhang, Y., Xu, W., Zhang, J., 2019. Rhizosphere formation and involvement in foxtail millet (*Setaria italica*) root growth under drought stress. *J. Integr. Plant Biol.* 61 (4), 449–462. <https://doi.org/10.1111/jipb.12716>.
- Llorens, E., Sharon, O., Camañes, G., García-Agustín, P., Sharon, A., 2019. Endophytes from wild cereals protect wheat plants from drought by alteration of physiological responses of the plants to water stress. *Environ. Microbiol.* 21 (9), 3299–3312. <https://doi.org/10.1111/1462-2920.14530>.
- Lozano, Y.M., Aguilar-Trigueros, C.A., Ospina, J.M., Rillig, M.C., 2022. Drought legacy effects on root morphological traits and plant biomass via soil biota feedback. *N. Phytol.* 236, 222–234. <https://doi.org/10.1111/nph.18327>.
- Lü, P., Zheng, Y., Chen, L., Ji, N., Yao, H., Maitra, P., Hu, H.-W., Li, X.-C., Guo, L.-D., 2020. Irrigation and fertilization effects on arbuscular mycorrhizal fungi depend on growing season in a dryland maize agroecosystem. *Pedobiol. (Jena.)* 83, 150687. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.pedobi.2020.150687>.
- Lupwayi, N.Z., Fernandez, M.R., Kanashiro, D.A., Petri, R.M., 2021. Profiles of wheat rhizobacterial communities in response to repeated glyphosate applications, crop rotation, and tillage. *Can. J. Soil Sci.* 101, 157–167. <https://doi.org/10.1139/cjss-2020-0008>.
- Ma, X., Zarebanadkouki, M., Kuzyakov, Y., Blagodatskaya, E., Pausch, J., Razavi, B.S., 2018. Spatial patterns of enzyme activities in the rhizosphere: Effects of root hairs and root radius. *Soil Biol. Biochem.* 118, 69–78. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.soilbio.2017.12.009>.
- Ma, X., Li, X., Ludewig, U., 2021. Arbuscular mycorrhizal colonization outcompetes root hairs in maize under low phosphorus availability. *Ann. Bot.* 127, 155–166. <https://doi.org/10.1093/aob/mcaa159>.
- Madejon, P., Fernandez-Boy, E., Morales-Salmeron, L., Navarro-Fernandez, C.M., Madejon, E., Domínguez, M.T., 2023. Could conservation tillage increase the resistance to drought in Mediterranean faba bean crops? *Ecol. Ecosyst. Environ.* 349, 108449 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.agee.2023.108449>.
- Mahdi, L.K., Miyauchi, S., Uhlmann, C., Garrido-oter, R., Langen, G., Wawra, S., Niu, Y., Guan, R., Robertson-Albertson, S., Bulgarelli, D., Parker, J.E., Zuccaro, A., 2022. The fungal root endophyte *Streptoporia vermicifera* displays inter-kingdom synergistic beneficial effects with the microbiota in *Arabidopsis thaliana* and barley. *ISME J.* 16, 876–889. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41396-021-01138-y>.
- Manjunatha, B.S., Nivetha, N., Krishna, G.K., Watts, A., Raipuria, R.K., Elangovan, A., Pushkar, S., Bandeppa, S., Chandrashekar, N., Asha, A.D., Chinnusamy, V., Aggarwal, C., Dukare, A.S., Paul, S., 2022. Plant growth-promoting rhizobacteria *Shewanella putrefaciens* and *Cronobacter dublinensis* enhance drought tolerance of pearl millet by modulating hormones and stress-responsive genes. *Physiol. Plant.* 174, e13676 <https://doi.org/10.1111/pp1.13676>.
- Meier, I.C., Timo, T., Heitk, J., Wrobel, T.J., Kandler, E., Marschner, B., Preusser, S., Leuschner, C., 2020. Root exudation of mature beech forests across a nutrient availability gradient: the role of root morphology and fungal activity. *N. Phytol.* 226, 583–594. <https://doi.org/10.1111/nph.16389>.
- Meier, M.A., Xu, G., Guerrero, M.G.L., Li, G., Smith, C., Sigmon, B., Herr, J.R., Alfano, J. R., Ge, Y., Schnable, J.C., Yang, J., 2022. Association analyses of host genetics, colonizing microbes, and plant phenotypes under different nitrogen conditions in maize. *eLife* 11, e75790. <https://doi.org/10.7554/eLife.75790>.
- Meisner, A., Jacquiod, S., Snoek, B.L., Ten Hooven, F.C., van der Putten, W.H., 2018. Drought legacy effects on the composition of soil fungal and prokaryote communities. *Front. Microbiol.* 9, 294. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fmicb.2018.00294>.
- Methe, B.A., Hiltbrand, D., Roach, J., Xu, W., Stuart, G., Goodner, B.W., Stapleton, A.E., 2019. Functional gene categories differentiate maize leaf drought-related microbial epiphytic communities. *PLoS One* 15 (9), e0237493. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0237493>.
- Mine, A., Berens, M.L., Nobori, T., Anver, S., Fukumoto, K., Winkelmüller, T.M., Takeda, A., Beckera, D., Tsuda, K., 2017. Pathogen exploitation of an abscisic acid- and jasmonate-inducible MAPK phosphatase and its interception by *Arabidopsis* immunity. *PNAS* 114 (28), 7456–7461. <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.1702613114>.
- Mofini, M.T., Diedhiou, A.G., Simonin, M., Dondjou, D.T., Pignoly, S., Ndiaye, C., Min, D., Vigouroux, Y., Laplaze, L., Kane, A., 2022. Cultivated and wild pearl millet display contrasting patterns of abundance and co-occurrence in their root mycobiome. *Sci. Rep.* 12, 207. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-021-04097-8>.
- Moore, E.R., Carter, K.R., Henegha, J.P., Steadman, C.R., Nachtsheim, A.C., Anderson-cook, C., Dickman, L.T., Newman, B.D., Dunbar, J., Sevanto, S., Albright, M.B.N., 2023. Microbial Drivers of Plant Performance during Drought Depend upon Community Composition and the Greater Soil Environment. *Microbiol. Spectr.* 11 (2) <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpls.2017.02223>.
- Müller, L.M., Bahn, M., 2022. Drought legacies and ecosystem responses to subsequent drought. *Glob. Change Biol.* 28 (17), 5086–5103. <https://doi.org/10.1111/gcb.16270>.
- Murali, M., Singh, S.B., Gowtham, H.G., Shilpa, N., Prasad, M., Aiyaz, M., Amruthesh, K. N., 2021. Induction of drought tolerance in *Pennisetum glaucum* by ACC deaminase producing PGPR- *Bacillus amyloliquefaciens* through Antioxidant defense system. *Microbiol. Res.* 253, 126891 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.micres.2021.126891>.
- Naylor, D., Degraaf, S., Purdom, E., Coleman-Derr, D., 2017. Drought and host selection influence bacterial community dynamics in the grass root microbiome. *ISME J.* 11, 2691–2704. <https://doi.org/10.1038/ismej.2017.118>.
- Naylor, D., Naasko, K., Smith, M., Couvillion, S., Nicora, C., Trejo, J., Fransen, S., Danczak, R., McClure, R., Hofmocker, K.S., Jansson, J.K., 2023. Interactive effects of depth and differential irrigation on soil microbiome composition and functioning. *Front. Micro* 2, 1078024. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fmicb.2023.1078024>.
- Nephali, L., Moodley, V., Piater, L., Steenkamp, P., Buthelezi, N., Dubery, I., Burgess, K., Huyser, J., Tugizimana, F., 2021. A Metabolomic Landscape of Maize Plants Treated With a Microbial Biostimulant Under Well-Watered and Drought Conditions. *Front. Plant Sci.* 12, 676632 <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpls.2021.676632>.
- Oberholster, T., Vikram, S., Cowan, D., Valverde, A., 2018. Key microbial taxa in the rhizosphere of sorghum and sunflower grown in crop rotation. *Sci. Total Environ.* 624, 530–539. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2017.12.170>.
- Ojuederie, O.B., Babalola, O.O., 2023. Growth enhancement and extension of drought stress in maize inoculated with multifaceted ACC deaminase producing rhizobacteria. *Front. Sustain. Food Syst.* 6, 1076844 <https://doi.org/10.3389/fsufs.2022.1076844>.
- Omotayo, O.P., Igiehon, O.N., Babalola, O.O., 2021. Metagenomic Study of the Community Structure and Functional Potentials in Maize Rhizosphere Microbiome: Elucidation of Mechanisms behind the Improvement in Plants under Normal and Stress Conditions. *Sustainability* 13, 8079. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su13148079>.
- Othibeng, K., Nephali, L., Myoli, A., Buthelezi, N., Jonker, W., Huyser, J., Tugizimana, F., 2022. Metabolic Circuits in Sap Extracts Reflect the Effects of a Microbial Biostimulant on Maize Metabolism under Drought Conditions. *Plants* 11, 510 <https://doi.org/10.3390/plants11040510>.
- Oyserman, B.O., Flores, S.S., Griffioen, T., Pan, X., Wijk, E., Van Der, Pronk, L., Lokhorst, W., Nurfikar, A., Paulson, J.N., Movvassagh, M., Stopnisek, N., Kupczok, A., Cordovez, V., Carrión, V.J., Ligterink, W., Snoek, B.L., Medema, M.H., Raaijmakers, J.M., 2022. Disentangling the genetic basis of rhizosphere microbiome assembly in tomato. *Nat. Commun.* 13, 3228. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41467-022-30849-9>.
- Pambuka, G.T., Kinge, T.R., Ghosh, S., Cason, E.D., Nyaga, M.M., Gryzenhout, M., 2022. Plant and Soil Core Mycobiomes in a Two-Year Sorghum-Legume Intercropping System of Underutilized Crops in South Africa. *Microorganisms* 10, 2079 <https://doi.org/10.3390/microorganisms10102079>.
- Pande, P.M., Azarbad, H., Tremblay, J., St-Arnaud, M., Yergeau, E., 2023. Metatranscriptomic response of the wheat holobiont to decreasing soil water content. *ISME Commun.* 3 (1), 1–13. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s43705-023-00235-7>.
- Paul, G.K., Mahmud, S., Dutta, A.K., Sarkar, S., Laboni, A.A., Hossain, S., Nagata, A., Karmaker, P., Razu, M.H., Kazi, T., Uddin, M.S., Zaman, S., Islam, M.S., Khan, M., Saleh, M.A., 2022. Volatile compounds of *Bacillus pseudomycoides* induce growth and drought tolerance in wheat (*Triticum aestivum* L.). *Sci. Rep.* 12, 19137 <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-022-22354-2>.
- Peng, Y., Xu, H., Li, B., Wang, X., 2023. Effects of intercropping and drought on soil aggregation and associated organic carbon and nitrogen. *Soil Use Manag* 39, 316–328. <https://doi.org/10.1111/sum.12866>.
- Pfeilmeier, S., Petti, G.C., Bortfeld-miller, M., Daniel, B., Field, C.M., Sunagawa, S., Vorholt, J.A., 2021. The plant NADPH oxidase RBOHD is required for microbiota homeostasis in leaves. *Nat. Microbiol.* 6, 852–864. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41564-021-00929-5>.
- Pivato, B., Semblat, A., Guégan, T., Jacquiod, S., Martin, J., Deau, F., Moutier, N., Lecomte, C., Burstin, J., Lemanceau, P., Malone, J.G., Monti, M., 2021. Rhizosphere Bacterial Networks, but Not Diversity, Are Impacted by Pea-Wheat Intercropping. *Front. Microbiol.* 12, 674556 <https://doi.org/10.3389/fmicb.2021.674556>.
- Qi, M., Berry, J.C., Veley, K.W., Connor, L.O., Finkel, O.M., Salas-gonzález, I., Kuhs, M., Jupe, J., Holcomb, E., Glavina, T., Creech, C., Liu, P., Tringe, S.G., Dangl, J.L., Schachtman, D.P., Bart, R.S., 2022. Identification of beneficial and detrimental bacteria impacting sorghum responses to drought using multi-scale and multi-system microbiome comparisons. *ISME J.* 16, 1957–1969. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41396-022-01245-4>.
- Qin, W., Liu, C., Jiang, W., Xue, Y., Wang, G., Liu, S., 2019. A coumarin analogue NFA from endophytic *Aspergillus fumigatus* improves drought resistance in rice as an antioxidant. *BMC Microbiol* 19, 50. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12866-019-1419-5>.
- Quiroga, G., Erice, G., Aroca, R., Chaumont, F., Ruiz-lozano, J.M., 2017. Enhanced Drought Tolerance by the Arbuscular Mycorrhizal Symbiosis in a Drought-Sensitive Maize Cultivar Is Related to a Broader and Differential Regulation of Host Plant Aquaporins than in a Drought-Tolerant Cultivar. *Front. Plant Sci.* 8, 1056. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpls.2017.01056>.
- Quiroga, G., Erice, G., Aroca, R., Zamarreño, Á.M., García-Mina, J.M., Ruiz-Lozano, J.M., 2018. Arbuscular mycorrhizal symbiosis and salicylic acid regulate aquaporins and root hydraulic properties in maize plants subjected to drought. *Agric. Water Manag.* 202, 271–284. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.agwat.2017.12.012>.

- Raaijmakers, B.J.M., Kiers, E.T., 2022. Rewilding plant microbiomes. *Science* 378 (6620), 599–600. <https://doi.org/10.1126/science.abn6350>.
- Rabbi, S.M.F., Warren, C.R., Macdonald, C., Trethowan, R.M., Young, I.M., 2022. Rhizosphere Soil-root interaction in the rhizosphere regulates the water uptake of wheat. *Rhizosphere* 21, 100462. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rhisp.2021.100462>.
- Raheem, A., Shaposhnikov, A., Belimov, A.A., Dodd, I.C., Ali, B., 2018. Auxin production by rhizobacteria was associated with improved yield of wheat (*Triticum aestivum* L.) under drought stress. *Arch. Agron. Soil Sci.* 64 (4), 574–587. <https://doi.org/10.1080/03650340.2017.1362105>.
- Renwick, L.L.R., Deen, W., Silva, L., Gilbert, M.E., Maxwell, T., Bowles, T.M., Gaudin, A.C.M., 2021. Long-term crop rotation diversification enhances maize drought resistance through soil organic matter. *Environ. Res. Lett.* 16, 084067 <https://doi.org/10.1088/1748-9326/ac1468>.
- Robertson-Albertyn, S., Terrazas, R.A., Balbirnie, K., Blank, M., Janiak, A., Szarejko, I., Chmielewska, B., Karcz, J., Morris, J., Hedley, P.E., George, T.S., Bulgarelli, D., 2017. Root hair mutations displace the barley rhizosphere microbiota. *Front. Plant Sci.* 8, 1094. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpls.2017.01094>.
- Rongsawat, T., Peltier, J., Boyer, J., Véry, A., Sentenac, H., 2020. Looking for Root Hairs to Overcome Poor Soils. *Trends Plant Sci.* 26 (1), 83–94. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tplants.2020.09.001>.
- Ruger, L., Ganther, M., Freudenthal, J., Jansa, J., Heintz-Buschart, A., Tarkka, M.T., Bonkowski, M., 2023. Root cap is an important determinant of rhizosphere microbiome assembly. *N. Phytol.* 239, 1434–1448. <https://doi.org/10.1111/nph.19002>.
- Ruiz-Lozano, J.M., Aroca, R., Zamarreño, Á.M., Molina, S., Andreo-Jiménez, B., Porcel, R., García-Mina, J.M., Ruyter-Spira, C., López-Ráez, J.A., 2016. Arbuscular mycorrhizal symbiosis induces strigolactone biosynthesis under drought and improves drought tolerance in lettuce and tomato. *Plant Cell Environ.* 39, 441–452. <https://doi.org/10.1111/pce.12631>.
- Sadhukhan, A., Prasad, S.S., Mitra, J., Siddiqui, N., Sahoo, L., Kobayashi, Y., Koyama, H., 2022. How do plants remember drought? *Planta* 256, 7. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00425-022-03924-0>.
- Salamon, S., Mikolajczak, K., Blaszczyk, L., Ratajczak, K., Sulewska, H., 2020. Changes in root-associated fungal communities in *Triticum aestivum* ssp. spelta L. And *Triticum aestivum* ssp. vulgare L. And drought stress and in various soil processing. *PLoS One* 15 (10), e0240037. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0240037>.
- Salas-gonzález, I., Rey, G., Flis, P., Custódio, V., Gopaulchan, D., Bakhoun, N., Dew, T. P., Suresh, K., Franke, R.B., Dangi, J.L., Salt, D.E., Castrillo, G., 2021. Coordination between microbiota and root endodermis supports plant mineral nutrient homeostasis. *Science* 371, 143. <https://doi.org/10.1126/science.abd0695>.
- Salem, M.A., Wang, J.Y., Al-babili, S., 2022. Metabolomics of plant root exudates: From sample preparation to data analysis. *Front. Plant Sci.* 10, 3389. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpls.2022.1062982>.
- Santos-Medellín, C., Edwards, J., Nguyen, B., Sundaresan, V., 2022. Acquisition of a complex root microbiome reshapes the transcriptomes of rice plants. *N. Phytol.* 235, 2008–2021. <https://doi.org/10.1111/nph.18261>.
- Santos-Medellín, C., Edwards, J., Liechty, Z., Nguyen, B., Sundaresan, V., 2017. Drought Stress Results in a Compartment-Specific Restructuring of the Rice Root-Associated Microbiomes. *MBio* 8 (4) e00764-17. <https://doi.org/10.1128/mbio.00764-17>.
- Santos-Medellín, C., Liechty, Z., Edwards, J., Nguyen, B., Huang, B., Weimer, B.C., Sundaresan, V., 2021. Prolonged drought imparts lasting compositional changes to the rice root microbiome. *Nat. Plants* 7, 1065–1077. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41477-021-00967-1>.
- Schlatterer, D.C., Kahl, K., Carlson, B., Huggins, D.R., Paulitz, T., 2020. Soil acidification modifies soil depth-microbiome relationships in a no-till wheat cropping system. *Soil Biol. Biochem.* 149, 107939.
- Schmidt, R.L., Azarbad, H., Bainard, L., Tremblay, J., Yergeau, E. (2023). Intermittent water stress favors microbial generalists that better help wheat under drought. *BioRxiv*. <https://doi.org/10.1101/2023.11.16.567418>.
- Schneider, H.M., Klein, S.P., Hanlon, M.T., Kaeppler, S., Brown, K.M., Lynch, J.P., 2020. Genetic control of root anatomical plasticity in maize. *Plant Genome* 13, e20003. <https://doi.org/10.1002/tpg2.20003>.
- Seitz, V.A., Mcgovern, B.B., Daly, R.A., Kresovich, S., Shields, L., Schipanski, M.E., Wrighton, K.C., Prenni, J.E., 2022. Variation in Root Exudate Composition Influences Soil Microbiome Membership and Function. *Applied. Environ. Microbiol.* 88 (11) <https://doi.org/10.1128/aem.00226-22>.
- Sendek, A., Karakoç, C., Wagg, C., Domínguez-begines, J., Martucci, G., Heijden, M.G.A. Van Der, Naz, A.A., Lochner, A., Antonis, C., Klotz, S., Gómez-aparicio, L., Eisenhauer, N., 2019. Drought modulates interactions between arbuscular mycorrhizal fungal diversity and barley genotype diversity. *Sci. Rep.* 9, 9650. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-019-45702-1>.
- Shao, M., Chen, Y., Gong, Q., Miao, S., Li, C., Sun, Y., Qin, D., Guo, X., Yan, X., Cheng, P., Yu, G., 2023. Biocontrol endophytes *Bacillus subtilis* R31 influence the quality, transcriptome and metabolome of sweet corn. *PeerJ* 11, e14967. <https://doi.org/10.7717/peerj.14967>.
- Shoaib, M., Banerjee, B.P., Hayden, M., Kant, S., 2022. Roots' Drought Adaptive Traits in Crop Improvement. *Plants* 11, 2256. <https://doi.org/10.3390/plants11172256>.
- Si, J., Froussart, E., Vienne, T., Vázquez-castellanos, J.F., Hamonts, K., Tang, L., Beirinx, S., Keyser, A., De, Deckers, T., Amery, F., Vandenabeele, S., Raes, J., Goormachtig, S., 2021. Interactions between soil compositions and the wheat root microbiome under drought stress: From an in silico to in planta perspective. *Comput. Struct. Biotechnol. J.* 19, 4235–4247. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.csbj.2021.07.027>.
- Siddiqui, N., Léon, J., Naz, A.A., Ballvora, A., 2021. Genetics and genomics of root system variation in adaptation to drought stress in cereal crops. *J. Exp. Bot.* 72 (4), 1007–1019. <https://doi.org/10.1093/jxb/era487>.
- Siebielec, S., Siebielec, G., Klimkowicz-pawlas, A., Galazka, A., Grzadzil, J., Stuczynski, T., 2020. Impact of Water Stress on Microbial Community and Activity in Sandy and Loamy Soils. *Agronomy* 10, 1429. <https://doi.org/10.3390/agronomy10091429>.
- Simmons, T., Styer, A.B., Pierroz, G., Gonçalves, A.P., Pasricha, R., Hazra, A.B., Bubner, P., Coleman-derr, D., Lebeis, S.L., Coleman-derr, D., 2020. Drought drives spatial variation in the millet root microbiome. *Front. Plant Sci.* 11, 599. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpls.2020.00599>.
- Sindhu, S.S., Sehrawat, A., Glick, B.R., 2022. The involvement of organic acids in soil fertility, plant health and environment sustainability. *Arch. Microbiol.* 204, 720. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00203-022-03321-x>.
- Singh, D., Mathimaran, N., 2019. Bioirrigation: a common mycorrhizal network facilitates the water transfer from deep-rooted pigeon pea to shallow-rooted finger millet under drought. *Plant Soil* 440, 277–292. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11104-019-04082-1>.
- Song, F., Han, X., Zhu, X., Herbert, S.J., 2012. Response to water stress of soil enzymes and root exudates from drought and non-drought tolerant corn hybrids at different growth stages. *Can. J. Soil Sci.* 92, 501–507. <https://doi.org/10.4141/CJSS2010-057>.
- Song, Y., Wilson, A.J., Zhang, X., Thoms, D., Sohrabi, R., Song, S., Geissmann, Q., Liu, Y., Walgren, L., He, S.Y., Haney, C.H., 2021. FERONIA restricts *Pseudomonas* in the rhizosphere microbiome via regulation of reactive oxygen species. *Nat. Plants* 7, 644–654. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41477-021-00914-0>.
- Spor, A., Roucou, A., Mounier, A., Bru, D., Breuil, M.C., Fort, F., Vile, D., Roumet, P., Philippot, L., Violle, C., 2020. Domestication-driven changes in plant traits associated with changes in the assembly of the rhizosphere microbiota in tetraploid wheat. *Sci. Rep.* 10, 12234. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-020-69175-9>.
- Stringlis, I.A., Yu, K., Feussner, K., de Jonge, R., Van Bentum, S., Van Verk, M.C., Berendsen, R.L., Bakker, P.A.H.M., Feussner, I., Pieterse, C.M.J., 2018. MYB72-dependent coumarin exudation shapes root microbiome assembly to promote plant health. *PNAS* 115 (20), 5213–5222. <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.1722335115>.
- Sun, C., Wang, R., Tang, G., Cai, S., Shi, H., Liu, F., Xie, H., Zhu, J., Xiong, Q., 2023a. Integrated 16S and metabolomics revealed the mechanism of drought resistance and nitrogen uptake in rice at the heading stage under different nitrogen levels. *Front. Plant Sci.* 14, 1120584. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpls.2023.1120584>.
- Sun, Y., Tao, C., Deng, X., Liu, H., Shen, Z., Liu, Y., Li, R., Shen, Q., Geisen, S., 2023b. Organic fertilization enhances the resistance and resilience of soil microbial communities under extreme drought. *J. Adv. Res.* 47, 1–12. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jare.2022.07.009>.
- Symanczik, S., Krützmann, J., Nehls, U., Boller, T., Courty, P., 2020. Expression of major intrinsic protein genes in *Sorghum bicolor* roots under water deficit depends on arbuscular mycorrhizal fungal species. *Soil Biol. Biochem.* 140, 107643. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.soilbio.2019.107643>.
- Szoboszlay, M., Lambers, J., Chappell, J., Kupper, J.V., Moe, L.A., McNear, D.H., 2015. Comparison of root system architecture and rhizosphere microbial communities of Balsas teosinte and domesticated corn cultivars. *Soil Biol. Biochem.* 80, 34–44. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.soilbio.2014.09.001>.
- Teixeira, P.L., Colaianni, N.R., Fitzpatrick, C.R., Dangi, J.L., 2019. Beyond pathogens: microbiota interactions with the plant immune system. *Curr. Opin. Microbiol.* 49, 7–17. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.mib.2019.08.003>.
- Tereucán, G., Ruiz, A., Nahuelcura, J., Oyarzún, P., Santander, C., Winterhalter, P., Ademar, P., Ferreira, A., Cornejo, P., 2021. Shifts in biochemical and physiological responses by the inoculation of arbuscular mycorrhizal fungi in *Triticum aestivum* growing under drought conditions. *J. Sci. Food Agric.* 102, 1927–1938. <https://doi.org/10.1002/jsfa.11530>.
- Tiziani, R., Miras-Moreno, B., Malacrin, A., Vescio, R., Lucini, L., Mimmo, T., Cesco, S., Sorgon, A., 2022. Drought, heat, and their combination impact the root exudation patterns and rhizosphere microbiome in maize roots. *Environ. Exp. Bot.* 203, 105071. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envexpbot.2022.105071>.
- Tripathi, B.M., Moroonyane, I., Sherman, C., Lee, Y.K., Adams, J.M., Steinberger, Y., Adams, J.M., Steinberger, Y., 2017. Trends in taxonomic and functional composition of soil microbiome along a precipitation gradient in Israel. *Microb. Ecol.* 74, 168–176. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00248-017-0931-0>.
- Umamathi, M., Chandrasekhar, C.N., Senthil, A., Kalaiselvi, T., Santhi, R., Ravikesavan, R., 2022. Isolation, characterization and plant growth-promoting effects of sorghum [*Sorghum bicolor* (L.) moench] root-associated rhizobacteria and their potential role in drought mitigation. *Arch. Microbiol.* 204, 354. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00203-022-02939-1>.
- Verbon, E.H., Liberman, L.M., Zhou, J., Yin, J., Pieterse, C.M.J., Benfey, P.N., Stringlis, I.A., Jonge, R.De, 2023. Cell-type-specific transcriptomics reveals that root hairs and endodermal barriers play important roles in beneficial plant-rhizobacterium interactions. *Mol. Plant* 16, 1160–1177. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.molp.2023.06.001>.
- Voothuluru, P., Mäkelä, P., Zhu, J., Yamaguchi, M., Cho, I.-J., Oliver, M.J., Simmonds, J., Sharp, R.E., 2020. Apoplastic Hydrogen Peroxide in the Growth Zone of the Maize Primary Root. Increased Levels Differentially Modulate Root Elongation Under Well-Watered and Water-Stressed Conditions. *Front. Plant Sci.* 11, 392. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpls.2020.00392>.
- de Vries, F., Lau, J., Hawkes, C., Semchenko, M., 2023. Plant-soil feedback under drought: does history shape the future? *Trends Ecol. Evol.* 38 (8), 708–718. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tree.2023.03.001>.
- de Vries, F.T., Brown, C., Stevens, C.J., 2016. Grassland species root response to drought: consequences for soil carbon and nitrogen availability. *Plant Soil* 409, 297–312. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11104-016-2964-4>.
- de Vries, F.T., Griffiths, R.I., Bailey, M., Craig, H., Giralanda, M., Gweon, H.S., Hallin, S., Kaisermann, A., Keith, A.M., Kretzschmar, M., Lemanceau, P., Lumini, E., Mason, K.

- E., Oliver, A., Ostle, N., Prosser, J.I., Thion, C., Thomson, B., Bardgett, R.D., 2018. Soil bacterial networks are less stable under drought than fungal networks. *Nat. Commun.* 9, 3033. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41467-018-05516-7>.
- de Vries, F.T., Williams, A., Stringer, F., Willcocks, R., McEwing, R., Langridge, H., L., S. A., 2019. Changes in root-exudate-induced respiration reveal a novel mechanism through which drought affects ecosystem carbon cycling. *N. Phytol.* 224, 132–145. <https://doi.org/10.1111/nph.16001>.
- de Vries, F.T., Griffiths, R.I., Knight, C.G., Nicolitch, O., Williams, A., 2020. Harnessing rhizosphere microbiomes for drought-resilient crop production. *Science* 368, 270–274. <https://doi.org/10.1126/science.aaz5192>.
- Wach, D., Skowron, P., 2022. An overview of plant responses to the drought stress at morphological, physiological and biochemical levels. *PJA* 50, 25–34. <https://doi.org/10.26114/pja.iung.435.2022.04>.
- Wagg, C., Hautier, Y., Pellkofer, S., Banerjee, S., Schmid, B., Heijden, M.G.A. Van Der, 2021. Diversity and asynchrony in soil microbial communities stabilizes ecosystem functioning. *eLife* 10, e62813. <https://doi.org/10.7554/eLife.62813>.
- Wang, J., Ding, Y., Cao, Y., Xu, W., Zhang, Y., 2021. Rhizosphere microbes induce root immune response under soil drying. *Plant Signal. Behav.* 16 (8), 1920752 <https://doi.org/10.1080/15592324.2021.1920752>.
- Wang, P., Lopes, L.D., Lopez-guerrero, M.G., Dijk, K., Van, Alvarez, S., Riethoven, J., Schachtman, D.P., 2022. Natural variation in root exudation of GABA and DIMBOA impacts the maize root endosphere and rhizosphere microbiomes. *J. Exp. Bot.* 73 (14), 5052–5066. <https://doi.org/10.1093/jxb/erac202>.
- Wang, T., Li, C., Wu, Z., Jia, Y., Wang, H., Sun, S., Mao, C., Wang, X., 2017. Abscisic acid regulates auxin homeostasis in rice root tips to promote root hair elongation. *Front. Plant Sci.* 8, 1121. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpls.2017.01121>.
- Wang, X.-B., Azarbad, H., Leclerc, L., Dozois, J., Mukula, E., Yergeau, É., 2022. A Drying-Rewetting Cycle Imposes More Important Shifts on Soil Microbial Communities than Does Reduced Precipitation. *mSystems* 7 (4). <https://doi.org/10.1128/mSystems.00247-22>.
- Wang, Y., Wang, X., Sun, S., Jin, C., Su, J., Wei, J., Luo, X., Wen, J., Wei, T., Sahu, S.K., Zou, H., Chen, H., Mu, Z., Zhang, G., Liu, X., Xu, X., Gram, L., Yang, H., Wang, E., Liu, H., 2022. GWAS, MWAS and mGWAS provide insights into precision agriculture based on genotype-dependent microbial effects in foxtail millet. *Nat. Commun.* 13, 5913. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41467-022-33238-4>.
- Watts-Williams, S.J., Emmett, B.D., Levesque-Tremblay, V., MacLean, A.M., Sun, X., Satterlee, J.W., Fei, Z., Harrison, M.J., 2019. Diverse *Sorghum bicolor* accessions show marked variation in growth and transcriptional responses to arbuscular mycorrhizal fungi. *Plant Cell Environ.* 42, 1758–1774. <https://doi.org/10.1111/pce.13509>.
- Webber, H., Ewert, F., Olesen, J.E., Müller, C., Fronzek, S., Ruane, A.C., Nendel, C., Bourgault, M., Martre, P., Ababaei, B., Bindi, M., Ferrise, R., Finger, R., Fodor, N., Gabaldón-leal, C., Gaiser, T., Jabloun, M., Kersebaum, K.-C., Lizaso, J.L., Wallach, D., 2018. Diverging importance of drought stress for maize and winter wheat in Europe. *Nat. Commun.* 9, 4249. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41467-018-06525-2>.
- Wen, Z., White, P.-J., Shen, J., Lambers, H., 2021. Linking root exudation to belowground economic traits for resource acquisition. *N. Phytol.* 233, 1620–1635. <https://doi.org/10.1111/nph.17854>.
- Williams, A., de Vries, F.T., 2020. Plant root exudation under drought: implications for ecosystem functioning. *N. Phytol.* 225, 1899–1905. <https://doi.org/10.1111/nph.16223>.
- Williams, A., Langridge, H., Straathof, A.L., Muhamadali, H., Hollywood, K.A., Goodacre, R., Vries, F.T. De, 2020. Root functional traits explain root exudation rate and composition across a range of grassland species. *J. Ecol.* 110, 21–33 <https://doi.org/10.1111/1365-2745.13630>.
- Wu, X., Hu, H., Li, S., Zhao, J., 2022. Chemical fertilizer reduction with organic material amendments alters co-occurrence network patterns of bacterium-fungus-nematode communities under the wheat-maize rotation regime. *Plant Soil* 473, 605–623. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11104-022-05314-7>.
- Xie, J., Wang, X., Xu, J., Xie, H., Cai, Y., Liu, Y., Ding, X., 2021. Strategies and structure feature of the aboveground and belowground microbial community respond to drought in wild rice (*Oryza longistaminata*). *Rice* 14, 79. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12284-021-00522-8>.
- Xu, F., Liao, H., Zhang, Y., Yao, M., Liu, J., Sun, L., Zhang, X., Yang, J., Wang, K., Wang, X., Ding, Y., Liu, C., Rensing, C., Zhang, J., Yeh, K., Xu, W., 2021a. Coordination of root auxin with the fungus *Piriformospora indica* and bacterium *Bacillus cereus* enhances rice rhizosphere formation under soil drying. *ISME J.* 16, 801–811. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41396-021-01133-3>.
- Xu, L., Coleman-derr, D., 2019. Causes and consequences of a conserved bacterial root microbiome response to drought stress. *Curr. Opin. Microbiol.* 49, 1–6. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.mib.2019.07.003>.
- Xu, L., Wang, A., Wang, J., Wei, Q., Zhang, W., 2017. *Piriformospora indica* confers drought tolerance on *Zea mays* L. through enhancement of antioxidant activity and expression of drought-related genes. *Crop J.* 5, 251–258. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cj.2016.10.002>.
- Xu, L., Naylor, D., Dong, Z., Simmons, T., Pierroz, G., Hixson, K.K., Kim, Y., Zink, E.M., Engbrecht, K.M., Wang, Y., Gao, C., DeGraaf, S., Maderaa, M.A., Sieverte, J.A., Hollingsworth, J., Birdseyef, D., Schellera, H.V., Hutmacher, R., Dahlberge, J., Coleman-Derr, D., 2018. Drought delays development of the sorghum root microbiome and enriches for monoderm bacteria. *PNAS* 115 (18), E4284–E4293. <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.1717308115>.
- Xu, L., Dong, Z., Chiniyqu, D., Pierroz, G., Deng, S., Gao, C., Diamond, S., Simmons, T., Wipf, H.M., Caddell, D., Varoquaux, N., Madera, M.A., Hutmacher, R., Deutschbauer, A., Dahlberg, J.A., Guerinot, M., Lou, Purdom, E., Ban, J.F., Taylor, J. W., Coleman-derr, D., 2021b. Genome-resolved metagenomics reveals role of iron metabolism in drought-induced rhizosphere microbiome dynamics. *Nat. Commun.* 12, 3209 <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41467-021-23553-7>.
- Yadav, B., Jogawat, A., Rahman, M.S., Narayan, O.P., 2021. Secondary metabolites in the drought stress tolerance of crop plants: A review. *Gene Rep.* 23, 101040 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.genrep.2021.101040>.
- Yan, B., Zhang, Y., Wang, Y., Rong, X., Peng, J., Fei, J., Luo, G., 2023. Biochar amendments combined with organic fertilizer improve maize productivity and mitigate nutrient loss by regulating the C-N-P stoichiometry of soil, microbiome, and enzymes. *Chemosphere* 324, 138293. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chemosphere.2023.138293>.
- Yang, L., Schröder, P., Vestergaard, G., Schlöter, M., Radl, V., 2020. Response of Barley Plants to Drought Might Be Associated with the Recruiting of Soil-Borne Endophytes. *Microorganisms* 8, 1414. <https://doi.org/10.3390/microorganisms8091414>.
- Yasuda, M., Ishikawa, A., Jikumaru, Y., Seki, M., Umezawa, T., Asami, T., Maruyama-nakashita, A., Kudo, T., Shinozaki, K., Yoshida, S., Nakashita, H., 2008. Antagonistic interaction between systemic acquired resistance and the abscisic acid-mediated abiotic stress response in arabidopsis. *Plant Cell* 20, 1678–1692. <https://doi.org/10.1105/tpc.107.054296>.
- Yigezu, Y.A., El-shater, T., Boughlala, M., Bishaw, Z., Niane, A.A., Maalouf, F., Degu, W. T., Wery, J., Boutifiras, M., Aw-Hassan, A., 2019. Legume-based rotations have clear economic advantages over cereal monocropping in dry areas. *Agron. Sustain. Dev.* 39, 58. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s13593-019-0602-2>.
- Yim, B., Ibrahim, Z., Rieger, L., Ganther, M., Maccario, L., Sørensen, S.J., Heintz, A., Mika, B., Doris, T.T., Michael, V., Evgenia, B., Blagodatskaya, E., Smalla, K., 2022. Soil texture is a stronger driver of the maize rhizosphere microbiome and extracellular enzyme activities than soil depth or the presence of root hairs. *Plant Soil* 478, 229–251. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11104-022-05618-8>.
- Zarei, T., Moradi, A., Kazemini, S.A., Akhgar, A., Rahi, A.A., 2020. The role of ACC deaminase producing bacteria in improving sweet corn (*Zea mays* L. var saccharata) productivity under limited availability of irrigation water. *Sci. Rep.* 1–12. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-020-77305-6>.
- Zhalnina, K., Louie, K.B., Hao, Z., Mansoori, N., Nunes, U., Shi, S., Cho, H., Karaoz, U., Loqué, D., Bowen, B.P., Firestone, M.K., Northen, T.R., Brodie, E.L., 2018. Dynamic root exudate chemistry and microbial substrate preferences drive patterns in rhizosphere microbial community assembly. *Nat. Microbiol.* 3 (4), 470–480. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41564-018-0129-3>.
- Zhang, W., Wang, J., Xu, L., Wang, A., Huang, L., Du, H., Qiu, L., Oelmüller, R., 2018. Drought stress responses in maize are diminished by *Piriformospora indica*. *Plant Signal. Behav.* 13 (1), e1414121 <https://doi.org/10.1080/15592324.2017.1414121>.
- Zhang, X., Kuzyakov, Y., Zang, H., Dippold, M.A., Shi, L., Spielvogel, S., Razavi, B.S., 2020a. Rhizosphere hotspots: Root hairs and warming control microbial efficiency, carbon utilization and energy production. *Soil Biol. Biochem.* 148, 107872 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.soilbio.2020.107872>.
- Zhang, X., Bilyera, N., Fan, L., Duddek, P., Ahmed, M.A., Carminati, A., Kaestner, A., Dippold, M.A., Spielvogel, S., Razavi, B.S., 2023. The spatial distribution of rhizosphere microbial activities under drought: water availability is more important than root-hair-controlled exudation. *N. Phytol.* 237, 780–792. <https://doi.org/10.1111/nph.18409>.
- Zhang, Y., Du, H., Xu, F., Ding, Y., Gui, Y., Zhang, J., Xu, W., 2020b. Root-Bacteria Associations Boost Rhizosphere Formation in Moderately Dry Soil through Ethylene Responses. *Plant Physiol.* 183, 780–792. <https://doi.org/10.1104/pp.19.01020>.
- Zhang, Y., Xu, F., Ding, Y., Du, H., Zhang, Q., Dang, X., Cao, Y., Dodd, I.C., Xu, W., 2021. Abscisic acid mediates barley rhizosphere formation under mild soil drying by promoting root hair growth and auxin response. *Plant Cell Environ.* 44, 1935–1945. <https://doi.org/10.1111/pce.14036>.
- Žiarovsk, J., Medo, J., Kysel, M., Zámiesková, L., Kacániiová, M., 2020. Endophytic Bacterial Microbiome Diversity in Early Developmental Stage Plant Tissues of Wheat Varieties. *Plants* 9 (266). <https://doi.org/10.3390/plants9020266>.
- Zilber-Rosenberg, I., Rosenberg, E., 2021. Microbial-driven genetic variation in holobionts. *FEMS Microbiol. Rev.* 45, 1–15. <https://doi.org/10.1093/femsre/fuab022>.